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Taxonomy of the anaerobic gut fungi (Neocallimastigomycota): a review of classification criteria and description of current taxa

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14 **Abstract.**

15 Members of the anaerobic gut fungi (Neocallimastigomycota) reside in the rumen and alimentary
16 tract of larger mammalian and some reptilian, marsupial, and avian herbivores. The recent
17 decade has witnessed a significant expansion in the number of described Neocallimastigomycota
18 genera and species. However, the lack of a centralized culture collection, coupled with
19 difficulties associated with their isolation and maintenance has greatly complicated comparative
20 studies to resolve inter- and intra-genus relationships. Here, we provide an updated outline of
21 Neocallimastigomycota taxonomy. We critically evaluate various morphological, microscopic,
22 and phylogenetic traits previously and currently utilized in Neocallimastigomycota taxonomy,
23 and provide an updated key for quick characterization of all genera. We then synthesize data
24 from taxa description manuscripts, prior comparative efforts, and molecular sequence data to
25 present an updated list of Neocallimastigomycota genera and species, with emphasis on
26 resolving relationships and identifying synonymy between recent and historic strains. We
27 supplement data from published manuscripts with information and illustrations from strains in
28 the authors' collections. Twenty genera and thirty-six species are recognized, but the status of ten
29 species in the genera *Caecomyces*, *Piromyces*, *Anaeromyces*, and *Cyllamyces* remains uncertain
30 due to the unavailability of culture and confere (*cf.*) strains, lack of sequence data, and/or
31 inadequacy of available microscopic and phenotypic data. Six cases of synonymy are identified
32 in the genera *Neocallimastix* and *Caecomyces*, and two names in the genus *Piromyces* are
33 rejected based on apparent misclassification.

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36 **I. Introduction.**

37 The kingdom fungi encompasses a bewilderingly diverse array of organisms that evolved from a
38 unicellular flagellated ancestor, and have since diversified to colonize a wide range of terrestrial,
39 freshwater, marine, engineered, and host-associated habitats [1]. Most fungi thrive as free-living
40 organisms, but many forge symbiotic, predatory, pathogenic, and commensal relationships with
41 algae [2], plants [3, 4], and animals [5, 6]. One of the most peculiar evolutionary trajectories and
42 niche adaptation events within the fungi is their sequestration into the herbivorous gut, an event
43 that spurred the evolution of a strictly anaerobic fungal lineage (the anaerobic gut fungi, phylum
44 Neocallimastigomycota) [7, 8]. Since their sequestration \approx 66 Mya [9], this fascinating group of
45 fungi has been blazing their own evolutionary trail; with multiple studies describing the impact
46 of fungal sequestration on their genome architecture, metabolic capacities, cellular structure, and
47 physiological preferences [10-13].

48 The history of the discovery and characterization of the anaerobic gut fungi spans more
49 than a century, although documenting their affiliation with the fungal kingdom [7, 14-16] and
50 isolating anaerobic gut fungal strains in pure cultures [17] were achieved relatively recently
51 (Figure 1). A study in 1843 surveyed “animalcules” in the stomach and intestine of herbivores
52 and carnivores, and observed small (10 μ m) motile propagules (fitting zoospore description) that
53 developed in large number in the horse caecum [18]. Subsequent reports described spherical and
54 ovoid flagellated structures with a single [19-21], or multiple flagella [20, 21] from the rumen
55 and horse caecum. These studies [19-21] have assumed that such structures were part of the
56 protozoan component of the herbivorous gut and proposed the names *Sphaeromonas*,
57 *Piromonas*, and *Oikomonas* for the single-flagellated and *Callimastix* for the polyflagellated
58 structures. The widespread occurrence of these flagellates (especially *Callimastix*) in the rumen,

59 feces, and hindgut of herbivores was subsequently confirmed in later publications [22, 23].
60 Warner [24, 25] and Orpin [26] were baffled by the observed huge fluctuation in numbers of
61 these flagellated structures pre and post feeding in sheep, a behavior unbecoming of organisms
62 thought to divide by binary fission, and suggestive of a pattern of growth involving spore
63 formation and release (although partitioning between the rumen lumen and wall, robust
64 chemotaxis, rapid lysis, and passive distribution of organisms attached to food material were put
65 forth as possible mechanisms to explain such fluctuations [24-26]). Finally, in a series of seminal
66 papers, Orpin unequivocally demonstrated through microscopic observation of sheep rumen fluid
67 and rumen material incubated with aqueous oat extracts under anaerobic conditions that the
68 polyflagellate *Neocallimastix* [7] and the monoflagellates *Sphaermonas* [16] and *Piromonas* [27]
69 are the zoosporic stage in the life cycle of a fungus, and that these zoospores could be induced to
70 produce rhizoidal structure with reproductive bodies (sporangia) that, in turn, release zoospores
71 to colonize plant materials. Subsequent studies not only confirmed such observations, but also
72 greatly expanded on the global diversity of the Neocallimastigomycota using culture-based and
73 culture-independent approaches [8, 28-32].

74 Taxonomic monographs serve to synthesize and analyze available data from disparate
75 sources spanning decades of research to provide a detailed, up-to-date description of a lineage of
76 interest. Ho and Barr [33] provided the last detailed monograph on the taxonomy of the
77 anaerobic gut fungi, covering the five genera described at the time of its publication (1995). This
78 landmark contribution remains an extremely valuable resource for Neocallimastigomycota
79 researchers. However, after more than a quarter century since its publication, we reason that an
80 updated detailed monograph on anaerobic gut fungal taxonomy is warranted for the following
81 reasons: 1. The need to account for the rapid progress in isolation and characterization of new

82 Neocallimastigomycota taxa reported in the last two decades; progress that led to the expansion
83 of reported Neocallimastigomycota genera from five (in 1995) to twenty. 2. The fact that many
84 Neocallimastigomycota type strains have been lost due to the difficulty in maintenance, lack of
85 institutional continuity, and the fact that no National Culture Collection accepts deposition of
86 anaerobic gut fungal strains; a situation that renders preservation and synthesis of currently
87 published data (and yet-unpublished observations) extremely valuable. 3: The shift in traits
88 deemed taxonomically informative in Neocallimastigomycota taxonomy: with the strong
89 emphasis on zoospores ultrastructure in earlier manuscripts [34] replaced by an increased
90 dependence on thallus and zoospores morphology [33] and in particular molecular phylogenetic
91 analysis [28, 29]. Such shift often requires revisiting historic strains, their isotypes, or *cf.* strains
92 to fill gaps in their microscopic description and molecular sequence data. 4. The utilization of
93 disparate vehicles for naming new taxa with various levels of characterization provided in such
94 vehicles: from detailed characterization manuscripts [35-37], taxonomic notes [38, 39], naming
95 strains as part of a broader genomic, systems biology, or biochemical studies [40, 41], or even
96 proposing names to accompany amplicon data in GenBank.

97 Here, we provide an updated monogram on the taxonomy of the Neocallimastigomycota.
98 We start by a detailed description of criteria (morphological, microscopic, and phylogenetic)
99 utilized in Neocallimastigomycota taxonomy. We then provide an updated key for quick
100 characterization of all Neocallimastigomycota genera. Finally, we provide a detailed description
101 of all taxa, with emphasis on history, nomenclature, occurrence, characteristics, and relationships
102 between recent and historic strains. We supplement data from published manuscripts by
103 information and figures from *cf.* strains of historic taxa, and of taxa of limited availability that
104 were obtained in the last decade as part of sustained isolation efforts by the authors' laboratories.

105 **II. Taxonomically informative criteria in Neocallimastigomycota taxonomy.**

106 Identification and classification of anaerobic gut fungi currently rely on a combination of
107 macroscopic (colony and liquid growth patterns), phenotypic (substrate utilization patterns and
108 enzymatic activities), microscopic, and sequence-based approaches. Microscopic
109 characterization involves identification and documentation of the wide patterns of shapes, sizes,
110 and overall developmental processes associated with all structures produced within the complex
111 life cycle of the Neocallimastigomycota. Molecular approaches involve utilizing various loci for
112 phylogenetic analysis.

113 **II.A. Microscopic criteria: The life cycle of anaerobic gut fungi.**

114 The Neocallimastigomycota undergoes a life cycle that involves the production and release of
115 motile flagellated spores (zoospores) from sporangia (Figure 2). These zoospores encyst,
116 germinate, and develop into a thallus structure that anchors the formation of new sporangia.
117 Multiple structures within the life cycle display considerable variability between taxa and could
118 hence be utilized for genus or species level delineation.

119 *II.A.1. Zoospores.* Anaerobic gut fungal spores range in size between 2.5 and 20 μm (Figure 3a).
120 However, size of spores can vary depending on the culturing conditions and stage of
121 development. Neocallimastigomycota spores are motile (i.e. zoospores) using flagellar
122 movements. Emphasis on flagellar ultrastructure in earlier taxa description manuscripts [34, 42,
123 43] was a reflection of the importance of such trait in Chytridiomycota taxonomy [44]. Such
124 emphasis has been waning, due to its complexity and the recognition that such feature is not
125 absolutely necessary for differentiation of anaerobic fungal taxa. On the other hand, the number
126 of flagella per zoospore is an extremely important trait for genus level delineation. Most genera
127 are monoflagellated, a term applied to taxa where the majority of zoospores have a single

128 flagellum (Figure 3a). In most “monoflagellated” taxa, some zoospores with two, three, and even
129 four flagella could be encountered (Figure 3b, c). A few taxa are steadfastly monoflagellated,
130 and have been referred to as “uniflagellated” (e.g. genus *Anaeromyces* [45-47]). No genus where
131 zoospores are predominantly bi, tri, or tetra flagellate has yet been identified. In the relatively
132 fewer polyflagellated Neocallimastigomycota genera described so far, the number of flagella per
133 zoospore ranges between 7-30 (Figure 3d). The evolution of multiple flagella is a unique trait of
134 these anaerobic fungi within the Opisthokonta (Fungi and metazoans) clade.

135 II.A.2. Cyst and Germ Tubes. Chemical and mechanical cues induce anaerobic fungal zoospores
136 to shed their flagella (Figure 3e-f), encyst (Figure 3f), and germinate (Figure 3g-h). Zoospore
137 encystment involves rounding up of the zoospore body and formation of a thick cell wall
138 between the plasma membrane and the cell surface layer. To our knowledge, no major
139 differences in size and morphology of cysts between taxa have been observed, and hence the cyst
140 shape and size are not taxonomically informative. Cysts germinate by producing germ tubes.
141 Some cysts produce a single germ tube (Figure 3g), while others produce two germ tubes (Figure
142 3h). The number of germ tubes per zoospore cyst is not a taxonomically informative trait as the
143 same isolate could produce one or more germ tubes. Germ tubes eventually grow and branch to
144 develop a rhizoidal system (Figure 3i-k).

145 II.A.3. Thallus development and sporangial formation mechanism. Thallus developmental
146 pattern is an extremely important trait for genus level delineation in the Neocallimastigomycota.
147 Two thallus development patterns have been described: monocentric and polycentric. In
148 monocentric thallus development, the nucleus stays within the spore and does not enter the germ
149 tube during germination, resulting in an anucleated rhizoidal system. As such, one center of
150 reproduction exists per thallus.

151 Two distinct mechanisms for sporangial formation are recognized in monocentric thalli:
152 endogenous and exogenous. Usually, monocentric genera exhibit both patterns during growth. In
153 endogenous monocentric thalli, the zoospore cyst enlarges and develops into the sporangium,
154 with anucleated rhizoidal growth originating from one side of the cyst (Figure 3l-o). However, it
155 is important to note that since multiple germ tubes often arise from a single cyst in opposite
156 directions as described above, a pseudo-intercalary sporangial development, in which sporangia
157 are positioned in the middle of two main rhizoidal systems (Figure 3p-q), could occur in some
158 endogenous monocentric species. The production of pseudo-intercalary sporangia could be a
159 taxonomically informative trait for species delineation. On the other hand, in exogenous
160 monocentric thalli, a bipolar germination of the zoospore cyst occurs. Here, anucleated rhizoids
161 develop at one end of the zoospore cyst. At the opposite end, a wider out-growth
162 (sporangiophore) develops at the end of which a sporangium is formed (Figure 3r). The nucleus
163 migrates out of the zoospore cyst into the sporangium (Figure 3s).

164 The second thallus developmental pattern known to occur in the anaerobic gut fungi is
165 polycentric thallus development. Here, the nuclei migrate out of the zoospore cysts into the germ
166 tube, which elongates and branches. Subsequent division of the nuclei in rhizoids give rise to
167 nucleated rhizoids, referred to as rhizomycelia (Figure 3t-u). The remaining empty zoospore cyst
168 can persist, but has no further function in thallus development.

169 In polycentric taxa, sporangia are developed terminally or intercalary. Terminal
170 sporangial development occurs in all polycentric taxa with one possible exception (*Orpinomyces*
171 *intercalaris*). Here, sporangia either develop at the end of sporangiophores (Figure 3v), or on
172 spherical vesicles (swellings at the hyphal tips). When developing on spherical vesicles, multiple
173 sporangia form, either directly on the vesicles (Figure 3w) or at the end of sporangiophores

174 (Figure 3x). Intercalary sporangial development pattern is observed in only a few polycentric
175 taxa. Here, sporangia develop as a lateral outgrowth of the hyphae (Figure 3y) or from hyphal
176 expansion (Figure 3z).

177 II.A.4. Sporangiphores. In monocentric taxa, sporangiophores are observed only during
178 exogenous, but not endogenous, sporangial formation. Similarly, in polycentric taxa,
179 sporangiophores are only observed in some terminal developmental patterns, as described above,
180 but not in intercalary development patterns. Sporangiphores vary in length from few microns to
181 600 μm , and various degrees of length variation has been observed between taxa (Figure 3aa-ab).
182 Some sporangiophores exhibit unique morphology that could be informative in delineating
183 genera and species, e.g. eggcup shape (Figure 3ac, arrow), or wide-flattened (Figure 3ad). Some
184 sporangiophores end with sub-sporangial swellings (apophysis) (Figure 3ae, arrow). In some
185 monocentric genera, sporangiophores are branched with two or more sporangia, resulting in
186 monocentric multispore thalli (Figure 3af-ag). Monocentric multispore thalli can be
187 easily distinguished from polycentric thalli by their anucleated rhizoids.

188 II.A.5. Sporangia. As described above, endogenous, pseudo-intercalary endogenous, and
189 exogenous sporangia could be observed in genera with monocentric thalli, while terminal and
190 intercalary sporangia could be observed in genera with polycentric thalli. The sporangial shape
191 could be highly pleomorphic in some taxa, while others exhibit a highly uniform single
192 sporangial shape. Shapes include globose (Figure 3ah), ellipsoidal with constriction at the middle
193 (Figure 3ai), ovoid (Figure 3aj), bowling pin-shaped (Figure 3ak), egg-shaped (Figure 3al),
194 pyriform (Figure 3am), heart-shaped (Figure 3an), triangular ((Figure 3ao), mucronate with a
195 pointed apex (Figure 3ap), elongated (Figure 3aq), ellipsoidal without constriction (Figure 3ar),
196 and rhomboidal (Figure 3as). Differences in size and shape between exogenous, endogenous, and

197 pseudo-intercalary sporangia within a single monocentric isolate is common. Media components
198 and growth conditions could further contribute to such variations. Similarly, differences in size
199 and shape between terminal and intercalary sporangia in a single polycentric isolate have also
200 been frequently observed. In addition to size and shape, some sporangia exhibit additional
201 features that could be taxonomically informative. For example, few taxa produce sporangia with
202 one or two papillae, i.e. having pointed protrusion at the distal end of the sporangia (Figure 3at-
203 au). Upon maturity, basal walls are formed to separate mature sporangia from sporangiophores
204 (Figure 3am). The sporangial necks (the point between sporangia and sporangiophore or
205 sporangia and rhizoid) could either be tightly constricted (Figure 3ah-ai), or broad (Figure 3aj).
206 The neck port (opening) could be narrow (Figure 3ai) or wide (Figure 3aj). The size, shape, and
207 level of pleomorphy of sporangial necks could be taxonomically informative.

208 It is important to note that polycentric genera often cease to produce sporangia and
209 zoospores. With repeated subculturing, isolates progressively lose the ability to produce
210 sporangia and only produce sporangiophores initials (Figure 3av). In addition, many polycentric
211 isolates lose their zoosporogenesis ability and produce sterile sporangia (Figure 3aw), which
212 makes their identification very challenging. In such cases, isolates grow by rhizomycelial
213 fragmentation (Figure 3ax), which is feasible due to their nucleated nature.

214 II.A.6. Spore release. Spore release could occur through an apical pore (Figure 3ay), via
215 rupturing of the sporangial wall (Figure 3az), or a combination of both. Spore release could be
216 facilitated by sporangial papillae (Figure 3at-au). Sporangia could either stay intact (Figure 3ay),
217 or completely disintegrate (Figure 3ba) after zoospore discharge. The mechanism(s) by which
218 zoospores are released could be taxonomically informative traits for distinguishing taxa at the
219 genus and species levels.

220 II.A.7. Rhizoidal growth pattern. Rhizoidal growth pattern is an extremely informative trait for
221 genus-level delineation in the Neocallimastigomycota. Taxa either produce filamentous rhizoids
222 (Figure 3bb) or bulbous rhizoids (Figure 3bc). Filamentous rhizoids are capable of penetrating
223 the plant fibers by their tapering ends, while bulbous rhizoids expand their spherical holdfasts
224 within plant tissue, physically rupturing the fibers from within.

225 The majority of genera exhibit a filamentous rhizoidal growth pattern, and produce two
226 types of hyphae (narrow and wide). Narrow hyphae are more frequently observed, especially in
227 monocentric taxa and do not seem to display much variation between taxa. Wide hyphae, usually
228 more readily visible in polycentric taxa, display multiple constrictions, which could either occur
229 at regular intervals resulting in a distinctive and taxonomically informative sausage-shaped
230 morphology (Figure 3bd), or at irregular intervals (Figure 3be). On the other hand, only two
231 Neocallimastigomycota genera exhibit bulbous rhizoidal growth pattern, with the production of
232 spherical holdfasts (Figure 3bc). Interestingly, a single isolate (identified as a member of the
233 genus *Cyllamyces* in the original publication, but see discussion on its identity in section IV.F
234 below) could conceivably represent a transition between both growth patterns, as it produces
235 elongated rhizoids in addition to intermittent bulbous holdfast (Figure 2e-f in [48]). The
236 prevalence, significance, and dependence on such feature on media composition and substrate
237 remains unclear.

238 Finally, anaerobic gut fungi can produce additional rhizoidal structures that accelerate
239 plant attachment and colonization, and such structures could be useful in taxonomic delineation.
240 Hyphal coils (Figure 3bf-bg) wrap around the plant fibers maximizing the contact area between
241 the hyphae and the plant. Appressoria (Figure 3bh-bi) develop as small protrusions on hyphae

242 that enlarge into multi-lobed vesicles with several penetration pegs, aiding in the penetration and
243 nutrients absorption from plant fibers.

244 II.A.8. Resting stages (resistant body) formation in the Neocallimastigomycota. The observations
245 that anaerobic gut fungi could be isolated from the saliva and dry fecal material of foregut and
246 hindgut fermenters [49-51]), that some strains could survive for prolonged time intervals without
247 subculturing [52], and that *Pecoramyces ruminantium* strain C1A could withstand relatively
248 extended times of air exposure [53] have led to postulations that yet-unidentified structure(s)
249 (referred to as resting stages or resistant bodies) could be produced as part of the life cycle of
250 some Neocallimastigomycota taxa. Such postulations have been augmented by the microscopic
251 observation of specific structures that do not directly fit into any of the life cycle phases
252 described above. Examples include spherical structures in a strain morphologically similar to *P.*
253 *communis* (Figure 6 in [54]), multichambered spore-like structures in *Anaeromyces* strains
254 AUC1/AUC2 (Figure 2 in [52]), *Buwchfawromyces eastonii* strain GE09 (Figure S1 F-G in
255 [37]), and *Khyollomyces* strain HoCa14.A2.2 [55] (Figure 3bj), as well as sporangial-like
256 structures developing at the tip of elongated thalli in a *Neocallimastix* sp. strain MC-2 (Figures 7
257 and 8 in [56]). In addition, the formation of peculiarly enlarged cells in *Pecoramyces*
258 *ruminantium* has been observed (Figure 3bk). Remarkably, these cells bear strong morphological
259 resemblance to titan cells: enlarged cells produced by *Cryptococcus neoformans* in response to
260 exposure to the lung environment and shown to enhance the survival and propagation of *C.*
261 *neoformans* [57]. In addition to putative induction by unfavorable conditions (air exposure or
262 resource depletion), Davies et al. [51] suggested that development of such structures could be
263 associated with the transition of fungal-associated biomass from the rumen to the feces.
264 However, conclusive information on the prevalence, composition, and role of putative resting

265 stages in the Neocallimastigomycota life cycle is lacking. As such, the value of their description
266 in current and future classification schemes remains uncertain.

267 II.A.9. Caveats associated with microscopic characterization of Neocallimastigomycota. As
268 described above, a wide range of microscopic variabilities occur in various life stages within the
269 Neocallimastigomycota. However, the sole utilization of microscopic features, especially for
270 species level delineation, could be tenuous due to three main reasons: First, a high level of
271 pleomorphy, especially in sporangia and sporangiophore shapes, is observed within individual
272 Neocallimastigomycota strains when grown in different media or even the same media. This is
273 especially true for monocentric genera like *Piromyces* (Figure S1a-h) and *Neocallimastix* (Figure
274 S1i-k). Many of such sporangial variations have unfortunately been used as defining criteria for
275 proposing and differentiating species within the genus *Piromyces* (see section IV.3. below).
276 Second, within polycentric taxa, the failure to produce sporangia (Figure S1l-m) or zoospores, or
277 the production of uncharacteristic sporangial shapes (Figure S1n) often renders their
278 identification challenging. Finally, difficulty in identifying the number of flagella (an important
279 criterion for generic level differentiation) on some spores might lead to erroneous reporting of
280 mono- and poly-flagellation (Figure S1o-p). Such pleomorphism or paucity in morphological
281 features hence necessitates the simultaneous use of molecular tools for the accurate identification
282 and characterization of anaerobic gut fungi. The concurrent use of both morphological and
283 molecular tools has greatly facilitated the description of most newly described genera, which
284 otherwise would not have been possible.

285 **II. B. Phylogenetic markers for Neocallimastigomycota taxonomy.**

286 Within the ribosomal operon (Figure 4a), various loci have been examined for their utility as
287 phylogenetic markers for Neocallimastigomycota taxonomy. Studies using the 18S rRNA and

288 the 5.8S rRNA subunits suggested their limited value in taxa resolution due to the high level of
289 sequence conservation, or short length, respectively [58]. However, these loci have proven useful
290 for detection [59] and quantification [60] of anaerobic gut fungi in environmental samples. The
291 use of the intergenic spacer (IGS) region has been restricted to molecular typing methods, e.g.
292 Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP), and reported only partial concordance with
293 genus-level assignments using microscopic features [61].

294 The two most extensively utilized loci for resolving Neocallimastigomycota taxonomy
295 are the internal transcribed spacer 1 (ITS1, Figure 4b), and the 28S large ribosomal subunit
296 (LSU), especially the 5' region covering the hypervariable D1 and D2 domains in the molecule
297 (D1/D2 LSU, Figure 4c). ITS1 has been used for ribotyping [62, 63] as well as sequence-based
298 analysis [64], a reflection of its wide utilization in broader mycological research [65]. However,
299 as previously demonstrated [28, 29, 66], the ITS1 locus in Neocallimastigomycota taxonomy
300 suffers from two main flaws: First, considerable sequence divergence is often encountered
301 between copies of the rRNA loci within a single strain [28, 29, 37], rendering accurate species
302 and strain level resolution challenging. Second, ITS1 length varies greatly between different
303 genera [28, 66], limiting its value in assessing inter-genus relationships and supra-genus
304 associations.

305 The use of the D1/D2 LSU region was first reported in RFLP-based surveys [61, 63], and
306 consequently proposed to resolve relationships between species of a single genus (*Orpinomyces*)
307 [67] and subsequently between various genera [68]. The lack of intra-strain sequence divergence,
308 as well as its uniform length (750-760 bp) across all genera renders it an appealing molecular
309 taxonomic marker [28]. Indeed, all taxa description manuscripts since 2015 reported D1/D2 LSU
310 sequences, and reference sequences for all genera have been generated [28]. Recently, a

311 concerted effort by the scientific community has produced a curated D1/D2 alignment with
312 representatives of all cultured and uncultured clades to facilitate taxonomic assessment and
313 diversity surveys (available at <https://anaerobicfungi.org/databases/>). Finally, efforts towards
314 utilizing the entire ribosomal operon for taxonomic assessment using long read nanopore
315 sequencing is currently underway (D. Young, personal communication).

316 Utilization of protein coding genes, e.g. elongation factor 1- α (*EFl α*), and two different
317 RNA polymerase II subunits (*RPB1* and *RPB2*) as phylogenetic markers for
318 Neocallimastigomycota taxonomy has been reported, but only as part of larger efforts to resolve
319 interphylum relationships within the kingdom fungi, and always utilizing very few strains [69].
320 Broader phylogenomic efforts have recently been contributing to resolving the phylum's position
321 within the fungal tree of life, as well as the relationship between various Neocallimastigomycota
322 genera. Utilizing a collection of 26 genomic and transcriptomic datasets, Wang et al. used a
323 concatenated set of 434 highly conserved and generally single-copy protein-coding genes in
324 fungi for phylogenetic inference using maximum likelihood and Bayesian approaches [9]. The
325 resulting work has led to a well-resolved phylogenomic tree that was congruent with D1/D2
326 LSU-generated phylogenetic outline.

327 **III. Key for the identification of currently described Neocallimastigomycota genera.** Twenty
328 anaerobic gut fungal genera have been described so far, based on a combination of growth
329 features, microscopic characteristics of various life cycle stages, and phylogenetic analysis [34-
330 37, 43, 45, 55, 70-75]. A key for the identification and differentiation of members of these
331 genera is presented below (Table 1). The key aims to provide an accurate, fast, and convenient
332 procedure for taxa identification. As such, preference is given to readily discernable macroscopic
333 (e.g. colony morphology, liquid growth pattern), and microscopic (thallus development, rhizoidal

334 growth pattern, and zoospore flagellation) features over more challenging characteristics, e.g.
335 zoospore ultrastructure, or genome- and transcriptome-based phylogenomic approaches.

336 Genera in the Necallimastigomycota exhibit either a monocentric or a polycentric thallus
337 developmental pattern. Such pattern could be determined by microscopically examining the
338 distribution of nuclei in preparations stained with nuclear stains, e.g. 4', 6' diamidino-2-
339 phenylindol (DAPI) or bisbenzimidazole. Polycentric taxa show nuclei throughout the thalli (Figure
340 3t-u), while in monocentric taxa, stained nuclei will be observed only in sporangia (Figure 3n-p,
341 s), although few could occasionally be observed in the sporangiophores in immature sporangia
342 before septum development.

343 Four polycentric genera have been described so far: *Orpinomyces*, *Anaeromyces*,
344 *Cyllamyces*, and *Paucimyces*. Further differentiation between these genera could be achieved via
345 observing spore flagellation patterns (*Orpinomyces* is unique among polycentric genera in
346 having polyflagellated zoospores n=12-24), rhizoidal growth pattern (*Cyllamyces* is unique
347 among polycentric genera in having a distinct bulbous growth pattern), hyphal morphology
348 (*Anaeromyces* is unique in having hyphal constrictions at regular intervals resulting in distinctive
349 sausage-shaped hyphae (Figure 3bb)), or sporangial developmental pattern (*Paucimyces* is
350 unique in producing spherical vesicles at the hyphal tip from which multiple sporangia develop,
351 Figure 3v-x). In addition, many of these genera exhibit unique macroscopic features that allow
352 for a quick tentative visual identification. For example, *Orpinomyces* strains generate a unique
353 cottony growth in liquid media that has not been observed in other genera, and *Orpinomyces*
354 colonies on roll tubes also tend to spread out sometimes to >1 cm in diameter (see detailed taxa
355 description and illustrations of the genus *Orpinomyces* below). *Anaeromyces* strains in liquid
356 media form thick pearl-like growth patterns (Figure S1 in reference [76]).

357 The majority of genera (16/20) are monocentric, and their rapid macroscopic or
358 microscopic differentiation could be more challenging. In monocentric genera, bulbous rhizoidal
359 growth pattern has been observed in one genus (*Caecomyces*), allowing for a relatively
360 straightforward identification. In addition, this genus is characterized by a granular colony
361 morphology, and a “sandy” growth in liquid media that resembles bacterial, rather than fungal
362 growth, and differentiates *Caecomyces* from other monocentric filamentous genera (see detailed
363 taxa description and illustrations of the genera *Caecomyces* and *Cyllamyces* below).

364 Within the remaining fifteen monocentric filamentous genera, four produce
365 polyflagellated zoospores (*Aestipascuomyces*, *Feramyces*, *Ghazallomyces*, and *Neocallimastix*).
366 These genera could be differentiated by their unique macroscopic or microscopic traits.

367 *Aestipascuomyces* strains are unique in their dual spore release mechanism through an apical
368 pore and sporangial dissolution. *Feramyces* strains produce medium-sized (3–7 mm), circular,
369 beige colonies with well-defined dark center and filamentous edges on solid media, and a thick
370 biofilm growth pattern in liquid media (Figure 1 in reference [71]). In contrast, *Neocallimastix*
371 strains produce smaller beige circular colonies (up to 2.5 mm) with a dark center of sporangial
372 structure, and a thin biofilm growth pattern in liquid media (see detailed taxa description and
373 illustrations of the genus *Neocallimastix* below). Finally, *Ghazallomyces* strains produce a
374 characteristic sporangial neck constriction (Figure 6d-g in reference [55]).

375 The eleven remaining genera all exhibit the same thallus development (monocentric),
376 rhizoidal growth (filamentous), and zoospore flagellation (monoflagellated) patterns. Most of
377 these genera could be identified based on unique microscopic features, e.g. extremely long
378 flagella in *Agriosomyces* zoospores (Figure 2a in [55]), papilla on the sporangia of
379 *Aklioshbomyces* (Figure 3at-au), presence of swollen sporangiophore (Figure 1e-h in [37]) and

380 twisted rhizoids (figure 1b in [37]) in *Buwchfawromyces*, formation of empty cup-shaped
381 sporangia after zoospore release in *Joblinomyces* (Figure 7c-f in [55]), branched sporangiophores
382 and multisporangiate thallus in *Khoyollomyces* (Figure 3af-ag), highly pleomorphic sporangial
383 shapes in *Liebetanzomyces* (Figures 2c-l, and 3a-f in [73]), constriction in the base of
384 sporangiophores (Figure 1d-e in [36]) and intercalary rhizoidal swelling (Figure 1f-g in [36]) in
385 *Oontomyces*, formation of thin fungal biofilm that attaches firmly to the tube's glass surface in
386 *Piromyces*, and formation of short sporangiophores and sub-sporangial swellings in *Tahromyces*
387 (Figure 9j-k in [55]). Nevertheless, the subtlety of many of these characteristics, and the fact that,
388 in most cases, only one species has been described for each of the genera described above,
389 renders molecular sequence identification necessary for confirmation.

390 **IV. Neocallimastigomycota genera and species.**

391 Progress in isolation and characterization of anaerobic gut fungal taxa has been a continuous, yet
392 uneven, process during the last \approx 45 years. Their strict anaerobic nature and extreme oxygen
393 sensitivity necessitate the mastery of the anaerobic Hungate techniques [77, 78] for their
394 isolation and maintenance. Additionally, although long-term storage procedures for various taxa
395 have been described [79-81], their efficacy and reliability vary greatly between strains. Finally,
396 senescence is frequently observed, with repeated subculturing often leading to either the
397 production of sporangia that do not differentiate to zoospores, or the outright failure to produce
398 sporangia [33]. Such difficulties have resulted in the loss of multiple historic strains, and are
399 reflected by the inability of national culture collections to maintain and preserve
400 Neocallimastigomycota isolates. Orpin reported a mixed bacterial-fungal culture with a single
401 fungal strain (*P. communis*) sole fungal strain in 1976 [27]. Successful isolation of anaerobic gut
402 fungi as a pure culture was first reported for *Sphaeromonas* and *Piromonas* from the horse

403 caecum [54], and *Neocallimastix* from the cow rumen [17, 82] in 1981. Heath et al. [34]
404 described the ultrastructure of the polyflagellate zoospore of a pure culture of *Neocallimastix*
405 *frontalis* [44]; and the manuscript represents the first formal description of an anaerobic gut
406 fungal genus. Gold et al. [43] used flagellar ultrastructure and life cycle description to
407 characterize two bulbous isolates, and proposed the name *Caecomycetes* for the flagellated
408 structures previously named *Sphaeromonas*. The same manuscript also proposed the name
409 *Piromycetes* as a substitute for *Piromonas*, although no characterization was reported for
410 *Piromycetes* in this paper. The genus *Piromycetes*, together with the novel genus *Orpinomyces* were
411 described the following year [70], and a fifth genus (*Anaeoromyces*) was subsequently described
412 in 1990 [45]. A notable lull in the description of new genera followed, with only one genus
413 (*Cyllamyces*) [74] described in the next quarter century. Recently, a rapid acceleration of the
414 pace of taxa description has occurred, with the description of 14 new genera from India, China,
415 the United Kingdom, Germany, and the USA since 2015 [35-37, 55, 71, 72, 75] (Figure 1). Such
416 expansion has been spurred by renewed interest in exploiting the biotechnological potential of
417 anaerobic gut fungi, for example for biofuel [83], value-added products [84], and secondary
418 metabolites [85].

419 Here, we synthesize data from taxa description manuscripts, comparative studies (e.g.
420 [46, 86, 87]), molecular sequence data, and examination of strains from our culture collection to
421 provide an updated list of Neocallimastigomycota genera and species. Genera are presented by
422 the chronological order of their discovery. Synonyms are proposed based on available molecular
423 and phenotypic data. In cases where the information to assess synonymy is inadequate, both
424 names are retained with a proposition to use a single name for describing future strains.
425 Uncertain affiliations based on inadequate descriptions are noted. Currently uncultured

426 alphanumeric genus-level clades identified only in culture-independent surveys (e.g. AL3, MN4,
427 SK3) are not included.

428 **1. *Neocallimastix*** Braune 1913 [20], Vavra and Joyon 1966 [88], Heath et al. 1983, [34].

429 *A. History.* The name “*Neocallimastix*” predates discovering the fungal nature of “rumen
430 flagellates” by Orpin [7]. Polyflagellated structures similar to *Neocallimastix* zoospores were
431 observed in 1913 [20], for which the name *Callimastix frontalis* was proposed. Vavra & Joyon
432 proposed that the *Callimastix* flagellate *C. cyclopsis* represents the dispersal phase of zoosporic
433 fungi and renamed it as *Neocallimastix* with *frontalis* as the type species [88]. Isolates belonging
434 to the genus *Neocallimastix* were first reported in 1981 [17] and the formal description of the
435 first isolate (*N. frontalis*, strain PN1) was provided by Heath *et al* in 1983 [34].

436 *B. Type: Neocallimastix frontalis* strain PN1, Figures 20-25 in [34]

437 *C GenBank sequences accession numbers:* No sequence data are available from the type strain.
438 Multiple morphologically identical *cf.* strains were subsequently isolated; and the earliest
439 deposited sequence data for *N. frontalis* is *N. cf. frontalis* isolate RE1 isolated from sheep rumen
440 [89], clones obtained in [66] MK036660.1-MK036676.1 (ITS1, 5.8S, ITS2), and KR920744
441 (LSU) obtained in [90].

442 *D. ID in Databases:* Mycobank ID: MB25486; Index Fungorum: IF25486; NCBI taxon ID:
443 4756.

444 *E. Diagnosis.* Description of the genus *Neocallimastix* is provided in [34], and expanded in [86]
445 and [33]. On solid agar media, *Neocallimastix* strains produce beige circular colonies (up to 2.5
446 mm) with a dark center of sporangial structure (Figure 6a). In liquid media, *Neocallimastix*
447 strains usually exhibit thin biofilm growth (Figure 6b). The genus *Neocallimastix* is
448 characterized by its polyflagellated zoospores (7-30 flagella, Figure 6c), monocentric thalli, and

449 filamentous rhizoids, with both endogenous (Figure 6d-e) and exogenous (Figure 6f-h)
450 sporangial development patterns.

451 *F. Occurrence.* Members of the genus *Neocallimastix* have been isolated from fecal and/or
452 rumen samples of cows (*Bos Taurus*) [91], water buffalo (*Bubalus bubalis*) [33], goat (*Capra*
453 *hircus*) [39], sheep (*Ovis aries*) [34, 38, 41, 82, 92-94], deer [28], sika deer (*Cervus nippon*) [95],
454 gaur (*Bos gaurus*) [96], elk (*Cervus canadensis*) [28], yak (*Bos grunniens*) [64], chamois
455 (*Rupicapra rupicapra*) [97], and alpine Ibex (*Capra ibex*) [98]. Culture-independent surveys
456 examining Neocallimastigomycota diversity in a large number of animal species suggest a
457 ubiquitous and highly abundant pattern of occurrence of the genus *Neocallimastix*, being
458 consistently encountered in the majority of examined animal species, and often representing a
459 large fraction of the overall community [28]. A higher prevalence in foregut over hindgut
460 fermenters [31], mirroring the isolation sources reported for most taxa, as well in captive over
461 wild animals [28], has also been proposed.

462 *G. List of Neocallimastix species.* The following names have been proposed for various
463 *Neocallimastix* isolates: *N. frontalis* [34, 88], *N. patriciarum* [93], *N. hurleyensis* [92], *N.*
464 *variabilis* [91], *N. cameroonii* [38], *N. californiae* [39], and *N. lanati* [41]. The potential
465 synonymy between the first four species (*N. frontalis*, *N. hurleyensis*, *N. patriciarum*, and *N.*
466 *variabilis* [91]) has previously been debated. *N. frontalis*, strain PN1 was isolated from the ovine
467 rumen, as previously described. *N. hurleyensis* was also isolated from the ovine rumen in 1985
468 [99], morphologically described in 1987 [100], but formally named in 1991 [92] as a
469 *Neocallimastix* species distinct from *N. frontalis* based on observed differences in flagellar
470 numbers and ultrastructure [92], and differences in zoospore release mechanisms, with *N.*
471 *hurleyensis* releasing zoospores through a single apical pore, as opposed to the dissolution of the

472 entire zoosporangial wall in *N. frontalis* [100]. Additional differences include the lack of
473 reference to exogenous sporangial development in *N. hurleyensis* description manuscript [92].
474 However, Ho and Barr [33] suggested that such differences could be attributed to differences in
475 growth conditions, inter-laboratory variations, or failure to observe a specific feature, and
476 proposed *N. hurleyensis* as a possible synonym of *N. frontalis*. Similarly, Ho and Barr [33]
477 argued for the lack of differences between *N. variabilis* and *N. frontalis*. *N. patriciarum*,
478 originally isolated by Orpin in 1975 and named *N. frontalis* [7], was subsequently assigned to *N.*
479 *patriciarum* [93] following the Latin description of *N. frontalis* by Heath et al. [34], and the
480 distinction between *N. patriciarum* (isolate CX of Orpin [7]) and *N. frontalis* (isolate PN1 of
481 Heath [34]) was mainly based on number of zoospore flagella, the presence or absence of an
482 equatorial constriction of the zoospore, flagellar ultrastructure differences, as well as major
483 fermentation end products and carbon source utilization patterns differences [93]. Finally,
484 Wubah and Fuller [86] compared type strain (PN1) of *N. frontalis* (isolate PN1 of Heath [34])
485 and *N. patriciarum* (isolate CX of Orpin [93]), and concluded that there are insufficient
486 microscopic differences to justify separating the two strains into two species.

487 We sought to further assess this potential synonymy using phylogenetic analysis. We
488 recognize that multiple gaps exist in availability of sequence data from original or *cf.* strains for
489 some taxa. We utilized ITS1 (Figure 5) and D1/D2 LSU sequence data (when available) from *cf.*
490 strains of *N. frontalis* (strain Re1, ITS1; strain SR4, LSU), *N. hurleyensis* (strain R1, ITS1), and
491 *N. patriciarum* (strain CX, LSU) to further examine potential synonymy. To our knowledge, no
492 sequence data from original or *cf.* strains are available for *N. variabilis*. Nineteen clones are
493 available for the *N. cf. frontalis* strain Re1. These clones are 0-5.65% divergent (average 0.82%).
494 The single ITS1 sequence available for the original *N. hurleyensis* strain R1 [52] diverges by

495 0.96-6.3% to the 19 *N. cf. frontalis* isolate Re1 clones (average 1.69%) (Figure 5), confirming
496 earlier morphological data that proposed synonymy of *N. hurleyensis* with *N. frontalis*.

497 The only available sequence for isolate CX, Orpin's original culture from which the *N.*
498 *patriciarum* type material was derived, covers the D1/D2 region of LSU and shows only 0.43%
499 divergence to *N. cf. frontalis* strain SR4 (currently the oldest *N. cf. frontalis* isolate with an
500 available D1/D2 LSU sequence in the database), again confirming earlier morphological data
501 that proposed synonymy of *N. patriciarum* to *N. frontalis*. As such, phylogenetic analysis
502 confirms potential synonymy previously proposed by microscopic examination for all four
503 species.

504 Synonymy could also be proposed for the three subsequently proposed species (*N.*
505 *cameroonii*, *N. californiae*, and *N. lanati*). Available molecular sequence data for these three
506 species include: LSU data from the type *N. cameroonii* isolate ABS CaDo3a, the whole region
507 encompassing ITS1-5.8S rRNA-ITS2-D1/D2 28S rRNA for an additional *N. cf. cameroonii*
508 strain (strain G3), ITS1 data as well as genomic sequences encompassing several rRNA loci
509 from *N. californiae* strain G1, and genomic sequences encompassing several rRNA loci from *N.*
510 *lanati*. Comparison of the ITS1, and the D1/D2 LSU regions of these *Neocallimastix* species
511 showed a high degree of similarity with only 0.58-1.72% divergence in the ITS1 region (Figures
512 4a, 5), and 0.15-0.56% divergence in the D1/D2 LSU region (Figure 4b). The available
513 microscopic data for *N. californiae* [39] does not provide conclusive evidence for clear
514 phenotypic differences when compared to *N. cameroonii*, and currently no microscopic data are
515 available for the effectively, but not yet validly, published *N. lanati*.

516 Interestingly, prior studies appear to have isolated, but misclassified, strains that are
517 highly related to *N. cameroonii*. Li and Heath [96] isolated a *Neocallimastix* species for which

518 they sequenced the ITS1 region, and designated this species as *N. cf. patriciarum*, but this
519 designation was not morphologically justified in the manuscript. Other strains with available
520 ITS1 sequences that were also assigned as *N. cf. patriciarum* strains are isolates NMW1 obtained
521 from Malaysian water buffalo [62], and isolate BTN1 (GQ355329.1) obtained from Indian cattle.
522 The % divergence between the ITS1 regions of these three *N. cf. patriciarum* ranged between
523 0.52-5.6% (Figure 5), suggesting they belong to the same species. The ITS1 sequences for all
524 three isolates were similar to *N. cameroonii* (1.2-4.3% divergence) (see below) (Figure 5),
525 suggesting that they are most probably synonyms to *N. cameroonii*.

526 As such, we propose retaining the following species for the genus *Neocallimastix*: *N.*
527 *frontalis* (synonyms *N. hurleyensis*, *N. variabilis*, *N. patriciarum* (Orpin), and *N. cameroonii*
528 (Syn. *N. californiae*, *N. cf. patriciarum*, and *N. lanati*).

529 **1.1. *Neocallimastix frontalis*:** Vavra and Joyon [88], Heath et al. [34].

530 = *Callimastix frontalis* Braune [20]

531 = *Neocallimastix variabilis* [91]

532 = *Neocallimastix hurleyensis* [92]

533 *Type strain:* *N. frontalis* (Strain PN1), Figures 20-25 in [34].

534 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* *N. cf. frontalis* isolate RE1: MK036660.1-MK036676.1
535 (ITS1, 5.8S, ITS2) clones obtained in [66], and KR920744 (LSU) obtained in [90]. No sequence
536 data are available from type strains. Multiple morphologically identical *cf.* strains were
537 subsequently isolated; and the earliest deposited sequence data is for *N. cf. frontalis* isolate RE1
538 isolated from sheep rumen [89].

539 *ID in Databases:* Mycobank: MB107058; Index Fungorum: IF: 107058I; NCBI taxon ID: 4757.

540 *Diagnosis.* Detailed descriptions are provided in [34, 86, 91]. Briefly, in addition to
541 characteristics provided in the description of the genus *Neocallimastix* above, the species is

542 characterized by endogenous and exogenous sporangial development; occasionally branched
543 sporangiophore; ellipsoidal, pyriform, or ovoid sporangia; lack of constriction or slight
544 constriction in sporangial necks; and release of zoospores through a sporangial rupture and
545 dissolution.

546 *Additional Illustrations:* *N. frontalis* strain Hef5, Oklahoma State University Culture Collection.
547 (Figure 6a-i).

548 **1.2. *Neocallimastix cameroonii*.** Ariyawansa et al. [38]

549 = *Neocallimastix californiae*. Li et al. [39]

550 = *Neocallimastix lanati*. Wilken et al. [41]

551 *Type strain:* ABS CaDo3a [38]

552 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* NG_060329.1 (D1/D2 LSU for type strain ABS

553 CaDo3a), MT085722.1 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-D1/D2 LSU for *N. cf. cameroonii* strain G3).

554 *ID in databases:* Mycobank: MB51212; Index Fungorum: IF51212; NCBI taxon ID: 17640372

555 *Diagnosis.* Original description provided in [38]. In addition to its phylogenetic distinction from

556 *N. frontalis* (Figure 5b-c) [38, 101]. The species is characterized by bifurcated rhizoidal system

557 at the base of sporangia (Figure 176 f in [38]), ovoid and spherical sporangia (Figure 176 d-f in

558 [38]), and the release of zoospores through a wide apical pore with the sporangial wall staying

559 intact (Figure 6m).

560 *5. Additional Illustrations:* *N. cf. cameroonii* strain G3 Oklahoma State University Culture

561 Collection (Figure 6j-m)

562 **2. *Caecomyces* (Gold et al. 1988)** [43]

563 *A. History.* Similar to the genus *Neocallimastix*, identification of members of the genus

564 *Caecomyces* predates the discovery of the fungal nature of “rumen flagellates”. zoospores of the

565 genus *Caecomyces* were first observed by Liebetanz [19] and Braune [20], for which the name

566 *Sphaeromonas* was proposed. It was not until 1976, when the affiliation of *Sphaeromonas*
567 *communis* with the fungi was confirmed [16], and its isolation in pure culture [54] soon
568 followed. The genus was formally described by Gold *et al*, based on the examination of two
569 isolates obtained from the feces of a horse [43]. A name change from *Sphaeromonas* to
570 *Sphaeromyces* to emphasize its fungal nature was unfeasible, since the name *Sphaeromyces* was
571 already in use. Therefore, the name *Caecomyces* was proposed for the genus based on the habitat
572 from which the isolates were obtained (the horse caecum).

573 *B. Type: Caecomyces communis* strain PN3. Figure 1, 2, 5-10 in [54]

574 *C. GenBank sequences accession numbers:* JF974109 (*Caecomyces cf. communis* GRL-11,
575 ITS1), JF974124 (*Caecomyces cf. communis* GRL-12, LSU). No sequence data are available
576 from type strains. Multiple morphologically identical *cf.* strains were subsequently isolated; and
577 the earliest deposited sequence data is for *Caecomyces cf. communis* GRL-11 and GRL-12.

578 *D. ID in databases.* Mycobank: MB25287; Index Fungorum: I IF25287; NCBI taxon ID: 4823.

579 *E. Diagnosis.* Description of the genus *Caecomyces* is provided in [43], and expanded in [87].

580 On solid media, *Caecomyces* produces small white granular colonies (Figure 6n). It exhibits
581 sandy morphology growth in liquid medium (Figure 6o); a reflection of its bulbous, non-
582 filamentous, rhizoidal growth, and its monocentric determinate growth pattern. *Caecomyces*
583 produces monoflagellated zoospores (Figure 6p), and exhibits a bulbous rhizoidal system with
584 spherical holdfasts, and monocentric thalli that are either uni- or multisporengiate.

585 *F. Occurrence.* Isolates of *Caecomyces* have been reported from horse (*Equus ferus*) feces [43,
586 54], cow rumen [13, 43, 102] and feces [87], Sheep salvia [94], rumen [103], and feces [40, 94],
587 fallow deer (*Dama dama*) feces [28], Yak rumen and feces [64], rumen and feces of water
588 buffalo [104], goat rumen [66], and alpine ibex feces [98]. Culture-independent diversity surveys

589 suggest the ubiquity of members of the genus *Caecomyces* in a wide range of foregut and
590 hindgut animals [28], although rarely representing the most dominant member of the community
591 [31], although a recent study has identified *Caecomyces* as the most abundant genus in fecal
592 samples from donkeys [105]). Further, it was observed that *Caecomyces* could form the majority
593 (30-90%) of colonies produced on-roll tubes from samples originating from animals that were
594 fed a specific diet (e.g. rice straw with molasses or palm press fiber [33]). Such observation
595 suggests an in-vivo niche selection and the ability of rapid propagation under specific nutritional
596 regimes.

597 *G. List of Caecomyces species.* The following *Caecomyces* species have been proposed: *C.*
598 *communis* [54], *C. equi* [43], *C. sympodiales* [102], and *C. churrovis* [40]. *Caecomyces*
599 *communis* [54] and *Caecomyces equi* [43] were initially distinguished by Gold et al. [43] based
600 on the presence of single bulbous rhizoid in *C. equi* as opposed to multiple bulbous rhizoids in *C.*
601 *communis*. However, subsequent studies [87] cast doubt on the distinctiveness of the two species
602 and argued that the number of bulbous rhizoids depends on the age of the culture, with younger
603 cultures more commonly display single bulbous holdfast, while multiple holdfasts develop as the
604 cultures age. Unfortunately, the unavailability of the type strain and lack of sequence data for *C.*
605 *equi* hampers further investigation into whether *C. equi* is a separate species from *C. communis*.
606 As such, we propose retaining the name *C. equi*, while using the more common species name “*C.*
607 *communis*” to describe future strains showing similar phylogenetic affiliation and phenotypic
608 traits.

609 Descriptions of *C. sympodialis* in [102] and *C. churrovis* in [40] demonstrate their
610 bulbous rhizoidal nature. Phylogenetically, *C. sympodialis* is distinct from *C. communis* (3.62%
611 divergence at the ITS1 level), and *C. churrovis* (4.25% divergence at the ITS1 level) (Figure 7).

612 However, only one *C. sympodialis* ITS1 sequence is available (and no D1/D2 LSU sequences),
613 rendering such assessment of phylogenetic distinction uncertain, given within strain ITS1
614 divergence commonly encountered in the Neocallimastigomycota. Microscopic characterization
615 also suggests a distinct pattern of thallus development (multi-sporangiate with sympodial
616 distribution of multiple sporangia on unbranched sporangiophores, see below) that is probably
617 not a function of growth condition or culture age. As such, the position of *C. sympodiales* as a
618 distinct species appears probable, in spite of the limited sequence data available.

619 Description of *C. churrovis* provided in [40] does not adequately ascertain phenotypic
620 distinction from *C. communis*. Further, *C. communis* and *C. churrovis* cluster together in both the
621 ITS1 (Figures 4a, 7), and the D1/D2 LSU trees (Figure 4b) with only 0.89%, and 0.77% average
622 sequence divergence, respectively. *C. churrovis* should hence be considered a synonym for *C.*
623 *communis*.

624 As such we propose retaining the following species for the genus *Caecomycetes*: *C.*
625 *communis* (synonym *C. churrovis*), *C. equi*, and *C. sympodialis*.

626 **2.1. *Caecomycetes communis* “comb. Nov.”** Gold et al. 1988 [43]

627 = *Sphaemonas communis* Orpin 1981, [54]

628 = *C. churrovis* [40]

629 *Type strain*: strain PN3 Figs. 1, 2, 5-10 in [16]

630 *GenBank sequences accession numbers*: JF974109 (*Caecomycetes cf. communis* GRL-11, ITS1),

631 JF974124 (*Caecomycetes cf. communis* GRL-12, LSU).

632 ID in databases Mycobank: MB1335565; Index Fungorum: IF135565; NCBI taxon ID: 4824.

633 *Diagnosis*. Original description is provided in [16] using in-vivo observations and enrichments,
634 with a brief description provided for the first isolate (designated H3) in [54]. Wubah and Fuller

635 [87] provide a more detailed description using a *cf.* strain isolated from cattle feces in Athens,
636 Georgia. *C. communis*, as described in all three studies display monoflagellated zoospores
637 (Figure 6p), monocentric thalli that are either uni- or multisporeangiate, and a bulbous rhizoidal
638 system with spherical holdfasts (Figure 6q-s). Both endogenous and exogenous sporangia are
639 observed. Endogenous sporangia are mainly globose (Figure 6q) and ovoid (Figure 6r).
640 Exogenous sporangia are typically observed at the end of long tubular sporangiophores and are
641 ovoid in shape (Figure 6s). Zoospore release mechanism was not observed, but sporangia were
642 frequently seen detached from the sporangiophore or the rhizoid (Figure 6t).
643 *Additional Illustrations.* *Caecomyces cf. communis* strain DS1 from Oklahoma State University
644 Culture Collection (Figure 6n-t).

645 **2.2. *Caecomyces equi*** Gold et al 1988 [43]

646 *Type strain:* strain PN3 from horse Caecum

647 *Nucleotide accession number:* NA

648 *ID in databases* Mycobank: MB135566, Index Fungorum: IF135566; NCBI taxon ID: NA.

649 *Diagnosis.* The description is similar to that of *C. communis*, with the possible differences of the
650 presence of single bulbous rhizoid (*C. equi*) or many bulbous rhizoids (*C. communis*), and the
651 production of predominantly unisporeangiate thalli (*C. equi*) as opposed to unisporeangiate or
652 multisporeangiate thalli by *C. communis* (but see [87] as stated above).

653 **2.3. *Caecomyces sympodialis*** Chen et al., 2007 [102].

654 **Type strain:** Strain W101 from rumen of yellow cow (*Bos indicus*).

655 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* DQ067604.1 (ITS1).

656 *ID in databases:* Mycobank: MB504777; Index Fungorum: IF504777; NCBI taxon ID: NA.

657 *Diagnosis*. Detailed description is provided in [102]. In addition to the general characteristics of
658 the genus *Caecomyces*, the species is unique in producing thalli with multiple sporangia (more
659 than three) that are sympodially distributed on long and tubular unbranched sporangiophores
660 (Figure i-k in [102]).

661 **3. *Piromyces*** Gold et al. 1988 [43]

662 *A. History*. Monoflagellated spores that are morphologically distinct from *Sphaeromonas*
663 *communis* (larger and more elongate) were reported by Liebetanez [19] and Braune [20], and
664 named *Piromonas communis*. Orpin characterized optimal growth conditions for *P. communis* in
665 rumen samples, partly described its sporangial and spore morphologies, and obtained a mixed
666 bacterial-fungal culture with *P. communis* as the sole fungal strain [27]. The name *Piromyces*
667 was suggested by Gold et al. in 1988 to emphasize the fungal, rather than protozoan, nature of
668 members of this genus; and detailed description of *P. communis* using isolates obtained from a
669 Holstein steer was published in in 1989 [70].

670 *B. Type: Piromyces communis* Figs 1, 5-10 in [27]

671 *C. GenBank sequences accession numbers*. The full ITS region of the original *P. communis*
672 strain P isolated by Orpin in 1977 from Clun Forest sheep rumen and preserved as a specimen
673 voucher at the Aberystwyth University biorepository (code ABS20-Pcomm01) was recently
674 (2020) sequenced and deposited in GenBank (accession number MW341535.1). The earliest
675 deposited D1/D2 LSU sequence data from a strain with the highest ITS1 sequence similarity to
676 *P. communis* strain P is for *Piromyces cf. communis* BRL-3 (GenBank accession number
677 JF974096).

678 *D. ID in database*: Mycobank ID: MB25332; Index Fungorum ID: IF25332; NCBI Taxon ID:
679 4821.

680 *E. Diagnosis.* Description of the genus *Piromyces* is provided in [70], and expanded in [33]. On
681 solid agar media, *Piromyces* produces small circular colonies with a dark center of sporangial
682 structure (Figures 6u). It exhibits thin biofilm-like growth in liquid medium that firmly attaches
683 to the glass walls of the tube (Figure 6v). Members of the genus *Piromyces* are characterized by
684 monocentric thalli (with both endogenous and exogenous sporangial development), filamentous
685 rhizoidal system, and monoflagellated zoospores (occasionally bi- to tetra-flagellated). Sporangia
686 display a variety of shapes, including globose, ovoid, pyriform, ellipsoidal, and elongated
687 (Figures 6w-ab).

688 *F. Occurrence.* Members of the genus *Piromyces* have been isolated from the feces, rumen, and
689 caecum of a wide range of animals, including, but not limited to, cows [28, 70], sheep [27, 28],
690 deer [28, 106], horses [28, 39, 107], donkeys (*Equus africanus*) [28, 108, 109], pony [109], asian
691 elephant (*Elephas maximus*) [107], water buffalo [110], and goats [111]. Similarly, culture-
692 independent diversity surveys often report a ubiquitous distribution for members of the genus
693 *Piromyces*, being consistently encountered in the majority of examined animal species, and often
694 representing a large fraction of the overall community [28, 31]. Samples where members of the
695 genus *Piromyces* constitute the entire AGF community has also been reported, e.g. fecal samples
696 of Black Rhinoceros and Pronghorn in [31].

697 *G. List of Piromyces species.* Traditionally, the genus *Piromyces* accommodated strains
698 displaying moncentric thalli, monoflagellated zoospores, and filamentous rhizoids. Following the
699 description of *P. communis* [70], several *Piromyces* species (*P. mae* [107], *P. dumbonicus* [107],
700 *P. rhizinflatus* [108], *P. spiralis* [111], *P. minutus* [106], and *P. citronii* [109]) displaying such
701 features were described between 1990 and 2000. While the type strain of *P. communis* originally
702 isolated by Orpin in 1977 [27] was preserved as a specimen voucher at the Aberystwyth

703 University biorepository (code ABS20-Pcomm01) from which ITS1 molecular sequence data has
704 been generated; no molecular sequence data are available to ascertain the phylogenetic affiliation
705 of *P. mae* [107], *P. dumbonicus* [107], *P. rhizinflatus* [108], *P. spiralis* [111], *P. minutus* [106],
706 and *P. citronii* [109]. Further, subsequent research has clearly demonstrated that the phenotype
707 of filamentous rhizoids, monocentric thalli, and monoflagellated zoospores is polyphyletic in the
708 Neocallimastigomycota [62]. Indeed, such phenotype was reported for ten additional genera
709 since 1995 [35-37, 55, 73]. Further, broad microscopic similarities between earlier described
710 *Piromyces* spp. and some of these newer genera have been noted [36, 55]. As such, the affiliation
711 of many of the earlier described species with the genus *Piromyces*, circumscribed based on
712 phylogenetic similarity to *P. communis*, could not be confirmed; and the fact that all these
713 isolates are currently extinct further hampers *Piromyces* taxonomy. For two of the *Piromyces*
714 species described since 2002 (*P. polycephalus* [110], *P. irregularis* [38]), molecular sequence
715 data is available. However, low ITS1 sequence similarity (78.6%, and 77.1%, respectively) to
716 *Piromyces communis* type strain P (MW341535.1) negates their affiliation to the genus
717 *Piromyces*. On the other hand, molecular sequence data confirm the affiliation of the latest
718 described *Piromyces* species (*P. finnis* [39]) with the genus *Piromyces*.

719 **3.1. *Piromyces communis***: Gold et al. [43]

720 = *Piromonas communis* [19, 27]

721 *Type strain*: *Piromyces communis* strain P, Figs 1, 5-10 in [27].

722 *GenBank sequences accession numbers*: MW341535.1 (ITS1, strain P isolated by Orpin and
723 preserved as a voucher specimen at Aberystwyth University) and JF974096 (D1/D2 region of
724 28S rRNA, *Piromyces cf. communis* BRL-3).

725 *ID in Databases*: Mycobank: MB 135567; Index Fungorum: IF135567; NCBI taxon ID: 4822.

726 *Diagnosis.* Detailed descriptions are provided in [70]. Briefly, in addition to characteristics
727 provided in the description of the genus *Piromyces* above, the species is characterized by mainly
728 globose zoospores that are monoflagellated. Biflagellated zoospores are also frequently
729 encountered. Endogenous sporangia are mostly globose and occasionally pyriform. Exogenous
730 sporangia are mostly elongated, although globose, ovoid, and irregular-shaped sporangia are also
731 observed. Sporangial neck is broad, and either not constricted or slightly constricted.
732 Sporangiphores vary in length, and could also display an eggcup shape. Zoospores are released
733 via an apical pore, followed by the dissolution of the entire sporangia wall.

734 *Additional Illustrations.* *Piromyces cf. communis* strain Jen1 from Oklahoma State University
735 Culture Collection (Figure 6u-y).

736 **3.2. *Piromyces mae.*** Li et al (1990) [107].

737 *Type strain:* *Piromyces mae* strain PN11.

738 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* NA

739 *ID in databases:* Mycobank: MB 126402; Index Fungorum: IF1 126402; NCBI taxon ID: NA.

740 *Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [107]. Briefly, in addition to characteristics
741 provided in the description of the genus *Piromyces* above, the species is characterized by
742 developing one, rarely two, papillae at their apex, through which spore release occurs; as well as
743 the formation of subsporangial swelling just below the sporangia.

744 **3.3. *Piromyces dumbonicus*** Li et al (1990) [107].

745 *Type strain:* *Piromyces dumbonicus* strain PN12

746 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* NA

747 *ID in databases:* Mycobank: MB 126401; Index Fungorum: IF1 126401; NCBI taxon ID: NA.

748 *Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [107]. The distinction between *P. dumbonicus* and
749 *P. communis* was mostly based on ultrastructural assessment, with no clear morphological or
750 microscopic differences reported.

751 **3.4. *Piromyces rhizinflatus*** Breton et al. 1991 [108].

752 *Type strain:* *Piromyces rhizinflatus* strain PS, Figure 1, 2 in [108].

753 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* NA

754 *ID in databases:* Mycobank: MB 276850; Index Fungorum: IF 276850; NCBI taxon ID: NA.

755 *Diagnosis:* Detailed description is provided in [108]. The species was isolated from dried feces
756 of Saharan donkey that was stored up to 150 days, implying a possible level of air-tolerance
757 [108]. The species was differentiated from other *Piromyces* species by the possession of a
758 pronounced neck constriction (to differentiate it from *P. communis*) and the lack of papilla (to
759 differentiate it from *P. mae*).

760 **3.5. *Piromyces minutus*** Ho et al. 1993 [106]

761 *Type strain:* *Piromyces minutus* strain D2.

762 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* NA.

763 *ID in databases:* Mycobank: MB: 360153; Index Fungorum: IF:360153; NCBI taxon ID: NA.

764 *Diagnosis:* Detailed description is provided in [106]. The species could be differentiated from
765 other *Piromyces* species by its sparingly branched rhizoidal structure and its markedly smaller
766 sporangia [106]

767 **3.6. *Piromyces spiralis*** Ho et al. 1993. [111]

768 *Type strain:* *Piromyces spiralis* strain G34.

769 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* NA

770 *ID in databases:* Mycobank: MB: 360467; Index Fungorum: IF: 360467; NCBI taxon ID: NA.

771 *Diagnosis:* Detailed description is provided in [111]. The species is characterized by extensive
772 coiling of the main rhizoid, the rapid dissolution of the sporangial wall; often leaving zoospores
773 clustered. As well, *P. spiralis* sporangia are mostly spherical, with a marked paucity of other
774 sporangial shapes in examined cultures.

775 **3.7. *Piromyces citronii*.** Gaillard-Martinie et al. 1995 [109]

776 *Type strain:* *Piromyces citronii* strain A1

777 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* NA

778 *ID in databases:* Mycobank: MB: 434478; Index Fungorum: IF: 434478; NCBI taxon ID: NA.

779 *Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [109]. The main difference between *P. citronii*
780 and most other *Piromyces* species is the production of a monocentric bi-, tri-, or multi-
781 sporangiate thallus (i.e. two, three, or more exogenous sporangia developing on the same
782 sporangiophore).

783 **3.8. *Piromyces finnis*** Li et al. 2016 [39]

784 *Type strain:* *Piromyces finnis* strain KS-2015.

785 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* KY399730 (ITS1).

786 *ID in databases:* Mycobank: MB: 551677; Index Fungorum: IF: 551677; NCBI taxon ID:
787 1754191.

788 *Diagnosis.* Description is provided in [39]. The species is phylogenetically distinct from *P.*
789 *communis*. In addition to general characteristics of the genus *Piromyces*, the species is
790 characterized by pleomorphic (mainly oval and club-shaped) sporangia, and the development of
791 a septum at the base of the sporangia.

792 *Additional Illustrations.* *Piromyces cf. finnis* strain DonB11 from Oklahoma State University
793 Culture Collection (Figure 6z-ab).

794 **4. *Orpinomyces* (Breton et al. 1989, Barr et al. 1989)**

795 *A. History.* Polycentric thallus development pattern has long been recognized in the Chytrid
796 genera *Nowakowskiella* and *Catenaria* [112, 113]. Within the Neocallimastigomycota,
797 polycentric thallus development was first reported in enrichments set up using cow's rumen fluid
798 and alfalfa or Bermuda grass as substrate [114, 115]. The first polycentric isolate was reported
799 by Breton et al. in 1989 [116] from the rumen of sheep. Although its polycentric nature was
800 recognized by the authors, the isolate was nevertheless described as a new species within the
801 genus *Neocallimastix*. Barr et al. [70] isolated a closely related strain from the cow rumen in
802 1989, and reasoned that the observed polycentric thallus merits the proposition of a new genus to
803 accommodate this strain. The genus name *Orpinomyces* (to honor Dr. Colin Orpin's
804 contributions) and the species name *bovis* were proposed.

805 *B. Type:* *Neocallimastix joyonii* (*Orpinomyces joyonii*) NJ1 [116]. Figure 1 and 2 in [116].

806 *C. GenBank sequences accession numbers:* AY429671 (ITS1, 5.8S, ITS2), JN939163 (D1/D2
807 LSU) (*Orpinomyces cf. joyonii* strain KF1). No sequence data are available from the type strains.
808 Multiple morphologically identical *cf.* strains were subsequently isolated; and the earliest
809 deposited sequence data is for an *O. cf. joyonii* strain KF1 is hence utilized as reference
810 sequence.

811 *D. ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB25326; Index Fungorum: IF25326; NCBI taxon ID:
812 37163.

813 *E. Diagnosis.* Description of the genus *Orpinomyces* is provided in [70] and expanded in [33].

814 *Orpinomyces* forms large (usually >1 cm diameter) white colonies on agar roll tubes (Figure
815 6ac). In liquid media, *Orpinomyces* displays a characteristic thick cottony fungal growth (Figure
816 6ad). These unique growth patterns allow tentative identification based on visual examination of

817 colonies and liquid growth. *Orpinomyces* produces polyflagellated zoospores, exhibits
818 polycentric thallus development and a filamentous rhizoidal growth pattern. Wide hyphae
819 usually displaying multiple constrictions at irregular intervals (Figure 6ae). Old cultures of
820 *Orpinomyces* tend to lose their ability to produce sporangia and only produce sporangiophores
821 initials (Figure 6af).

822 *F. Occurrence.* Species of *Orpinomyces* have been isolated from cow rumen [33, 70, 117],
823 buffalo rumen [33], sheep rumen [116], as well as fecal samples of American bison (*Bison bison*)
824 and alpaca (*Lama pacos*) [28], cows [28, 118], sheep [52], water buffalo [67], and Yak [64].
825 Culture-independent diversity surveys suggest that members of the genus *Orpinomyces* almost
826 invariably constitute a minor fraction of the community when encountered, and are more
827 prevalent in foregut herbivores [28, 31].

828 *G. List of Orpinomyces species.* Two *Orpinomyces* species are currently recognized;
829 *Orpinomyces joyonii* [70, 116, 119], and *Orpinomyces intercalaris* [117] (Figure 4b). Breton *et*
830 *al* 1989 [116] reported on the isolation and characterization of a novel strain with polycentric
831 thallus and polyflagellated zoospores, for which the name *Neocallimastix joyonii* was proposed.
832 Shortly thereafter, Barr *et al.* [70] isolated another strain from the rumen of a Holstein steer for
833 which the name *Orpinomyces bovis* was first proposed. A detailed comparison between *O. bovis*
834 and *N. joyonii* was conducted by Li *et al* 1991 [119], and the authors concluded that both isolates
835 represented the same genus and species based on their morphological similarities. The
836 combination *Orpinomyces joyonii* was hence proposed: *Orpinomyces* for the genus name to
837 recognize these strains as the first representative of a new genus, and *joyonii* for the species
838 name to recognize the priority of Breton *et al.* over Barr *et al.*). The second species *Orpinomyces*
839 *intercalaris* was subsequently isolated and characterized in 1994 [117].

840 **4.1. *Orpinomyces joyonii*** Breton et al. [108], Li et al. [116, 119]
841 = *Orpinomyces bovis* Barr et al. [70]
842 = *Neocallimastix joyonii* Breton et al. [119]
843 *Type: Neocallimastix joyonii* strain NJ1 (= *Orpinomyces Joyonii*) = *Orpinomyces Bovis*. [70,
844 116]. Figure 1 and 2 in [116].
845 *GenBank sequences accession numbers. O. cf joyonii* strain KF1: AY429671 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2),
846 JN939163 (D1/D2 LSU). Sequence data from strains originally isolated by [70, 116] are not
847 available. The earliest deposited sequence data for an *O. cf joyonii* strain (strain KF1 from rumen
848 fluid of cows in Prague, Czech Republic) is hence utilized as reference sequence.
849 *ID in databases:* Mycobank ID: MB127934, Index Fungorum: IF127934; NCBI taxon ID: 48250
850 *Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [70, 116] as well as [118] for *O. cf. joyonii* strain
851 KF1. In addition to the general characteristics of the genus described above, *O. joyonii* produces
852 globose polyflagellated zoospores with 10-25 flagella (Figure 6ag). Sporangia are mainly
853 globose (Figure 6ah-aj) and developed either terminally at the tip of sporangiophores (Figure
854 6ah-ai) or as a lateral outgrowth of hyphae (Figure 6aj).
855 *Additional illustration. O. joyonii* strain D4A, from Oklahoma State University Culture
856 collection (Figure 6ac-aj).
857 **4.2. *Orpinomyces intercalaris*:** Ho et al. 1994 [117].
858 *Type strain.* Strain 19-2a [117]. Figs. 1-10 in [117].
859 *GenBank sequences accession numbers. O. cf. intercalaris* strain SKP: HQ703471 (D1/D2 LSU).
860 ITS1: NA. Original molecular data from strain 19-2a [117] are not available. The earliest
861 deposited sequence data for an *O. cf. intercalaris* (strain SKP1 from water buffalo rumen,
862 Haryana, India) is hence utilized as the reference sequence.

863 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB 357919, Index Fungorum: IF 357919; NCBI taxon ID:
864 1049955

865 *Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [117] and expanded in [33]. In addition to the
866 general characteristics of the genus, *O. intercalaris* is characterized by the production of globose
867 and intercalary sporangia (developed as expansion of the hyphae or as a lateral outgrowth of
868 hyphae), while terminal sporangia are rarely observed. Also, *O. intercalaris* is characterized by
869 the presence of zoospore cyst as an empty persistent structure attached to the rhizomycelium.
870 These criteria differentiate it from *O. joyonii*, in addition to their phylogenetic distinction. Upon
871 maturation, two septa are formed to separate the intercalary sporangium from the hyphae.
872 Zoospores are released through rupturing the sporangial wall followed by complete collapse of
873 the sporangial wall. Hyphae of *O. intercalaris* are constricted at regular intervals resulting in a
874 sausage-shaped appearance, as opposed to the constrictions observed at irregular intervals in *O.*
875 *joyonii* hyphae.

876 **5. *Anaeromyces*** Breton et al. 1990 [45]

877 =*Ruminomyces* Ho et al. 1990 [47]

878 *A. History.* The first representative of the genus *Anaeromyces* (*A. mucronatus*) was isolated from
879 the cow rumen in 1990 [45]. Shortly thereafter, a highly similar strain was reported (also from
880 the cow rumen), for which the name *Ruminomyces elegans* [47] was proposed. Precedence was
881 given to the genus name *Anaeromyces* over *Ruminomyces* [33].

882 *B. Type:* *Anaeromyces mucronatus* strain BF2 from the rumen of a cow [45]. Fig 1 in [47].

883 *C. GenBank sequences accession numbers.* *A. cf. mucronatus* strain (strain JF1 MW899528
884 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-D1/D2 LSU). No sequence data are available from type strains. Multiple

885 morphologically identical *cf.* strains were subsequently isolated; and the earliest deposited
886 sequence data is for *A. cf. mucronatus* strain (strain JF1 isolated from deer fecal samples).
887 *D. ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB27188; Index Fungorum: IF27188; NCBI taxon ID:
888 105135.

889 *E. Diagnosis.* Description of the genus *Anaeromyces* is provided in [45, 47], and expanded in
890 [33]. On solid media, *Anaeromyces* forms circular white colonies (4-6 mm in diam., Figure S1A
891 in [76]). In liquid, it forms thick, pearl-like growth (Figure S1b in [76]). *Anaeromyces* produces
892 monoflagellated zoospores (Figure 3E in [76]), exhibits polycentric thallus development (Figure
893 2A-B in [76]), and filamentous rhizoidal growth pattern (Figure 2C in [76]). Zoospores are
894 typically small, globose, and always monoflagellated (uniflagellated) with a flagellum length 16–
895 20 μm), with a rough, uneven surface. Terminal sporangia are typically mucronate with an
896 acuminate apex (Figure 3C in [76]). *Anaeromyces* produces wide and narrow hyphae, with
897 frequent constrictions in the wide hyphae resulting in a unique sausage-like appearance (Figure 1
898 D-E in [76]). Sporangogenesis and spore formation often cease after repeated subculturing, with
899 new biomass development and formation of new nuclei occurring through hyphal propagation.

900 *Occurrence.* *Anaeromyces* strains have been isolated from the cow rumen [45, 47], sheep rumen
901 [120] and feces [39], deer, European bison (*Bison bonasus*), and American bison [118], cows,
902 goats [76], as well as American bison and alpaca [28], as well as cattle and water buffalo [121].
903 Culture-independent analysis reported the presence of *Anaeromyces*-affiliated sequences in
904 26/30, and 8/21 of the samples examined in [31], and [28], respectively. These studies also
905 documented the occurrence of *Anaeromyces* beyond the typical foregut ruminants from which
906 they were isolated by detecting them in fecal samples from some hindgut fermenters (e.g. horses
907 and donkeys). In all studies, *Anaeromyces*-affiliated sequences typically represent a minor

908 component of the overall community in examined samples.

909 *List of Anaeromyces species.* Four species of *Anaeromyces* have so far been described: *A.*
910 *mucronatus* [45], *A. elegans* [47], *A. robustus* [39], and *A. contortus* [76]. Similar to the situation
911 of *Caecomyces communis* and *C. equi*, the lack of sequence data in the original papers that
912 described *A. mucronatus* [45] and *A. elegans* [47], the relatively minor differences between
913 representatives of both species, which could be a function of the growth conditions or mere
914 overlooking specific characteristics in the original description, and the absence of original
915 cultures, render confident ascertainment of the relationship between *A. mucronatus* and *A.*
916 *elegans* impossible. Therefore, we propose retaining the names *A. mucronatus* and *A. elegans*,
917 but only using *A. mucronatus* (and refraining from usage of the name *A. elegans*) to describe any
918 new related isolates, a practice that has already been followed in subsequent isolation efforts [28,
919 118]. *A. contortus* is phylogenetically and morphotypically distinct from *A. mucronatus/elegans*.

920 *A. robustus* represents a unique case that might justify future assignment to another genus
921 (*Capellomyces*), or a new genus pending additional availability of data. *A. robustus* description
922 [39] reports multiple unique features when compared to all other *Anaeromyces* species. The
923 zoosporangia have a distinct morphology previously unreported within the
924 Neocallimastigomycota, where they are club-shaped, and occasionally fuse to form a whale's
925 tail-like appearance. This is in contrast to the mucronate sporangia with acuminate apex typically
926 observed in other *Anaeromyces* species. The zoospores are described as having several
927 posteriorly directed flagella [39], implying a polyflagellated strain, in contrast to the
928 monoflagellated zoospores observed in other *Anaeromyces* spp. Further, the species appear to
929 lack the unique sausage-like hyphal morphology observed in other *Anaeromyces* species [39],
930 and a convincing demonstration of the polycentric nature of *A. robustus* via DAPI staining is

931 lacking in [39]. Interestingly, ITS-1 sequence data of *A. robustus* (KU057354.1) places it outside
932 of the *Anaeromyces* clade, and closer to members of the genus *Capellomyces* (Figure 8), and
933 D1/D2 LSU sequences data for this strain is currently unavailable. Pending availability of
934 additional information, the status of this species remains questionable. The unique morphology
935 of sporangia, coupled to the apparent lack of fundamental *Anaeromyces* traits could either
936 suggest affiliation with the genus *Capellomyces*, known to exhibit a wide range of sporangial
937 morphology, or as a distinct new genus within the *Anaeromyces-Liebetanzomyces-*
938 *Capellomyces-Oontomyces* clade.

939 **5.1. *Anaeromyces mucronatus*** Breton et al. 1990 [45] isolated from the rumen of a cow.

940 *Type strain.* *Anaeromyces mucronatus* strain BF2 from the rumen of a cow [45], Fig 1 in [47].

941 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* MW899528 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-D1/D2 LSU). Sequence
942 data from strain BF2 originally isolated by is not available. The earliest deposited sequence data
943 for an *A. cf. mucronatus* strain (strain JF1 isolated from deer fecal samples from Prague, Czech
944 Republic) is hence utilized as reference sequence.

945 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB 361273; Index Fungorum Registration Identifier IF 361273;
946 NCBI taxon ID: 994854

947 *Diagnosis.* Detailed description is given in [45] and expanded in [33, 47], In addition to general
948 genus-level characteristics, the species is characterized by terminal elliptical sporangia with
949 pointed apex, spherical exclusively monoflagellated (uniflagellated) zoospores, and sausage-
950 shaped hyphae.

951 **5.2. *Anaeromyces elegans*** Ho et al. 1990 [47]

952 = *Ruminomyces elegans* isolated from the rumen of a cow.

953 *Type strain.* Lectotype Figs 1-3 in [47]

954 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* NA.
955 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB 360152; Index Fungorum: IF360152; NCBI taxon ID: NA.
956 *Diagnosis.* The species show high similarity to *A. mucronatus*. The main difference is the
957 presence of an appressorium structure, i.e. lobed-like hyphal structures thought to facilitate the
958 penetration of plant cell walls. However, as described above, such presence could have been
959 overlooked in the original description of *A. mucronatus*. Zoospores are monoflagellated and
960 spherical (Figure 3c-d in [47]). Mature sporangia are mainly ellipsoidal and fusiform with
961 acuminate apices (Figure 2a-b,3a in [47]). Sporangia are developed terminally at the tip of
962 sporangiophores. Zoospores are released through a transverse slit of the sporangial wall which
963 stays intact after the zoospore release (Figure 3e in Ref 46). Hyphae exhibit the unique sausage-
964 like appearance with tight constrictions at regular intervals (Figure 3a in [47]).

965 **5.3. *Anaeromyces robustus*** Li et al. 2016 [39] from sheep feces.

966 *Type strain.* S4 (University of California Santa Barbara Culture Collection)

967 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* NR_148182.1 (ITS). No D1/D2 LSU sequence
968 available.

969 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB 551676; Index Fungorum: IF 551676; NCBI taxon
970 ID:1754192.

971 *Diagnosis.* *A. robustus* is differentiated from other *Anaeromyces* species by having distinct club-
972 shaped sporangia that occasionally fuse to form a whale's tail-like appearance. The zoospores
973 possess several posteriorly directed flagella [39], implying a polyflagellated strain. The hyphae
974 lack the unique sausage-like morphology observed in other *Anaeromyces* species [39],

975 **5.4. *Anaeromyces contortus*** (Hanafy et al. 2018) [76] from cow and goat feces

976 *Type Strain.* O2, Figure 1e in [76]

977 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* MG605693, MG605698, MG605708 (ITS1), and
978 MF121931 (D1/D2 LSU) sequence available.
979 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB 821369; Index Fungorum Registration Identifier: IF
980 821369; NCBI taxon ID: 2170304
981 *Diagnosis.* Detailed description is given in Hanafy et al [76]. In addition to phylogenetic
982 distinction from the *A. mucronatus* (Figure 4b-c, Figure 8), the species differs from *A.*
983 *mucronatus* and *A. elegans* in two main features: First: the production of the globose intercalary
984 sporangia in addition to the mucronate terminal sporangia observed in *A. mucronatus* and *A.*
985 *elegans* sporangia, and second: The formation of highly coiled and entangled hyphal structures
986 that are similar to traps produced by many nematophagous fungi [76].

987 **6. *Cyllamyces* Ozkose et al. 2001.**

988 *A. History.* The first representative of the genus *Cyllamyces* (*C. aberensis*) was described in 2001
989 [74] from cow feces, and a second species (*C. icaris*) was reported in 2014 from the feces of a
990 water buffalo [48].

991 *B. Type:* Strain EO14 (AFTOL 846), Figs. 1–11 in [74].

992 *C. GenBank sequences accession numbers:* AY997042 (ITS1, 5.8S, ITS2) and DQ273829
993 (D1/D2 LSU).

994 *D. ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB28540; Index Fungorum: IF28540; NCBI taxon ID:
995 324620.

996 *E. Diagnosis.* The genus *Cyllamyces* accommodates strains that produce bulbous holdfasts
997 (similar to the genus *Caecomyces*), but display polycentric thallus developmental pattern (as
998 opposed to the monocentric pattern in *Caecomyces*). Differences in morphological and
999 microscopic characteristics between members of the two genera are majorly reflecting the

1000 difference between their determinate (monocentric) versus indeterminate (polycentric) thallus
1001 developmental patterns. *Cyllamyces* colonies on solid media (Figure 6ac) are granular and beige-
1002 colored colonies, similar to *Caecomyces*, but are typically larger in size, a characteristic of all
1003 polycentric genera. In liquid media, *Cyllamyces* isolates usually aggregate into relatively large
1004 and loose granular brown clumps (Figure 6ad, compared to the fine granular, often sandy-like,
1005 smaller clumps in *Caecomyces* (Figure 6o). However, the bulbous nature of the rhizoidal growth
1006 results in much smaller clumps when compared to filamentous polycentric genera (*Orpinomyces*,
1007 *Anaeromyces*, and *Paucimyces*).

1008 *Cyllamyces* strains produce bulbous holdfast, with one or multiple sporangiophores
1009 arising from the holdfast. Each sporangiophore produces multiple spherical sporangia. The
1010 strains' polycentric nature is reflected by their capacity to produce as many as 12 sporangia per
1011 thallus (and up to five per a single sporangiophore) as well as the observation of nuclei
1012 throughout the entire thallus (i.e. in the holdfast, sporangiophores, and sporangia (Figures 8-9 in
1013 [74]). In comparison, *Caecomyces* spp. are monocentric, with no observed nuclear migration
1014 through the thallus. As well, *Caecomyces* produces single holdfasts per thallus each bearing a
1015 single sporangium, although the production of more than one holdfast and multiple sporangia has
1016 also been observed, as described above [87]. Similar to *Caecomyces*, *Cyllamyces* produces
1017 monoflagellated zoospores (Figure 5ae).

1018 *F. Phylogenetic relationship between the bulbous genera Caecomyces and Cyllamyces.*

1019 Phylogenetic analysis using ITS1 and D1/D2 LSU regions indicate that the bulbous genera
1020 *Caecomyces* and *Cyllamyces* constitute a single monophyletic clade within the
1021 Neocallimastigomycota (Figure 4b-c). A recent study that timed *Neocallimastigomycota*
1022 diversification events using highly conserved and generally single-copy genes from

1023 transcriptomic datasets strongly indicates that bulbous rhizoidal growth pattern evolved
1024 relatively recently (≈ 10 Mya) [9]. However, while the monophyly of bulbous
1025 Neocallimastigomycota is undisputed, the relationship between the genera *Caecomyces* and
1026 *Cyllamyces* is less clear. Phylogenetic analyses using ITS1 and D1/D2 LSU loci often provide
1027 conflicting tree topologies. For example [37] and [101] place *Cyllamyces* as an internal node
1028 within the broader *Caecomyces* in ITS1 [37], and D1/D2 LSU [37, 101] phylogenetic trees,
1029 respectively. Such pattern has led to suggestions of either splitting the genus *Caecomyces* into
1030 two genera [66], or reassigning *Cyllamyces* isolates as members of the genus *Caecomyces*. On
1031 the other hand, the analysis by Wang et al. using ITS1, entire ITS, and D1/D2 LSU regions
1032 produced variable topologies that were dependent on the marker and tree building algorithm
1033 utilized [64]. As well, topologies presented in [28, 31, 55] places both genera as two distinct
1034 separate clades. These variable outcomes are clearly a reflection of the paucity of strains
1035 included in the analysis; and interpretation of the observed results are often complicated by the
1036 unclear and possibly erroneous designations of strains in public databases. As well, the
1037 availability of only a single ITS1 sequence for some strains provides an incomplete picture of the
1038 breadth of diversity of the strain.

1039 Here, we conducted phylogenetic analysis using ITS1 using 10 strains of *Caecomyces*
1040 and *Cyllamyces* reliably characterized as monocentric (*Caecomyces* strains Cado13a, OF1, DS1,
1041 GRL-11, JH-2017a, W101) or polycentric (*Cyllamyces* strains AFTOL-ID 846, EO17, CB3B1,
1042 and TSB2) using Maximum Likelihood (Figure 7). The resulting topology shows clear
1043 separation between the two clades comprising *Caecomyces communis* and *Cyllamyces aberensis*
1044 (Figure 7). The positions of *Cyllamyces icaris* and *Caecomyces sympodialis* are the exception.
1045 Only one ITS1 sequence is available for each of these species, and these two sequences cluster

1046 together (with only 1.83% divergence). The two sequences diverge from *Caecomyces communis*
1047 clade by 5.36%, and 3.95%, respectively, and from *Cyllamyces aberensis* clade by 4.6%, and
1048 2.68%, respectively. This suggests that *Cyllamyces icaris* and *Caecomyces sympodialis* could
1049 putatively represent a third distinct bulbous genus (Figure 7). However, the presence of only a
1050 single ITS1 sequence from each of these species, and the absence of any LSU data preclude any
1051 further phylogenetic delineation. Indeed, microscopic descriptions in both manuscripts show a
1052 remarkable morphological resemblance, e.g. development of multiple sporangiophores from the
1053 bulbous holdfast, with multiple sporangia (usually more than 3) growing on the end of these
1054 sporangiophores (Figure 6 in [102] and (Figure 4 in [48]), and the thallus developmental patterns
1055 (monocentric in *Caecomyces sympodialis* and polycentric in *Cyllamyces icaris*) are not
1056 convincingly demonstrated in both manuscripts.

1057 Therefore, we reason that phylogenetic analysis (using the admittedly relatively few
1058 sequence data available), as well as morphological and microscopic distinctions described above
1059 that reflect differences in thallus development patterns (a trait consistently regarded as a genus-
1060 level differentiation phenotype) support retaining *Cyllamyces* as a distinct separate genus within
1061 the Neocallimastigomycota. Future assessments would require isolation and thorough
1062 characterization, loci sequencing, and comparative genomic and transcriptomic analysis of
1063 multiple strains from both clades in a single comparative study. A third bulbous genus comprised
1064 of *Cyllamyces icaris* and *Caecomyces sympodialis* is also possible given the available limited
1065 phylogenetic data, and the morphological and microscopic similarities between the two isolates
1066 [48, 102].

1067 *G. Occurrence.* *Cyllamyces* strains have been isolated from Cow feces [74], Buffalo feces [48]
1068 and rumen, and Tunis sheep (RA Hanafy, unpublished results). Sequences affiliated with the

1069 genus *Cyllumyces* has previously been assigned to the alphanumeric candidate genera MN1[122]
1070 and SP8 [30]. Culture-independent surveys identified members of the genus *Cyllumyces* (based
1071 on monophyly and high sequence identity to *C. aberensis* ITS1 [31], or LSU [28]) sequences in a
1072 wider range of animals, but still detected a clear preference to members of the Bovidae,
1073 especially domesticated cows.

1074 *H. List of Cyllumyces species*

1075 **6.1. *Cyllumyces aberensis*** Ozkose et al. 2001 [74] from cow feces

1076 Type strain: EO14 (=AFTOL-ID 846), Figs. 1–11 in [74].

1077 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* AY997042 (ITS1, 5.8S, ITS2) and DQ273829 (D1/D2
1078 LSU).

1079 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB28540; Index Fungorum Registration Identifier: IF28540;
1080 NCBI taxon ID: 324620.

1081 *Diagnosis.* Description is provided in detail in Ozkose et al. 2001 [74], *C. aberensis* produces
1082 spherical monoflagellated zoospores, polycentric thalli, and a single bulbous holdfast with
1083 multiple sporangia (Figure 1-5 in [74]). Multiple unbranched sporangiophores are developed
1084 from different part of the bulbous holdfast (Figure 5 in [74]). Branched sporangiophores were
1085 frequently encountered (Figure 6 in [74]). Sporangia are spherical or ovoid born terminally at the
1086 end of the sporangiophore (Figure 5-6 in [74]). Nuclei are observed in sporangia,
1087 sporangiophores, and the bulbous holdfasts (Figure 8-9 in [74]).

1088 *Additional Illustration:* *Cyllumyces cf. aberensis* strain TSB2 from Oklahoma State University
1089 Culture collection (Figure 6ak-al), and CFH681 (Figure 6am-ap) and BFH688 (Figure 6aq) from
1090 Agharkar Research Institute, Pune, India culture collection.

1091 **6.2. *Cyllumyces icaris*.** Sridhar et al. from the feces of a water buffalo [48].

1092 *Type strain.* CB3B1

1093 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* EU043229 (ITS1, 5.8S, ITS2).

1094 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: 629693; Index Fungorum Registration Identifier: IF 629693;

1095 NCBI taxon ID: NA.

1096 *General characteristics.* The description of *C. icaris* is provided in [48]. The authors

1097 differentiate *C. icaris* from *C. aberensis* based on its production of multiple holdfasts, larger

1098 sporangia, smaller number of sporangia per sporangiophore, and rudimentary filamentous growth

1099 structure in addition to bulbous growth pattern [48]. Phylogenetic analysis based on a single

1100 ITS1 sequence proves distinction from *C. aberensis* (average sequence divergence of 4.6%).

1101 However, while the described strain certainly appears distinct from *C. aberensis*, its affiliation as

1102 member of the genus *Cyllamyces*, rather than *Caecomyces*, or its affiliation with a third bulbous

1103 genus altogether, could not be conclusively ascertained from the provided information as

1104 detailed above. No evidence for polycentric thallus development in strain CB3B1 (i.e. DAPI

1105 stain showing nuclear migration to holdfasts and sporangiophores) is provided; and data on

1106 colony characteristics and liquid growth are also absent. The described patterns of multiple

1107 holdfast and multisporangiate growth have been observed in *Caecomyces* spp., as stated above

1108 [33, 87].

1109 **7. *Buwchfawromyces* (Callaghan et al. 2015).**

1110 *A. History.* The genus has one species, *B. eastonii*, isolated from feces of an Asian water buffalo

1111 [37]. The strain was originally classified as a member of the genus *Anaeromyces*. However, clear

1112 differences in morphological and microscopic features, as well as phylogenetic analysis using

1113 ITS1 and D1/D2 LSU loci clearly justified its accommodation in a new genus, for which the

1114 name *Buwchfawromyces* was proposed [37].

1115 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [37]. *Buwchfawromyces* produces
1116 monoflagellated zoospores, exhibits monocentric thalli development, and filamentous rhizoidal
1117 growth pattern. Zoospores are relatively large (9–11 μm) with a long (30–40 μm) single
1118 flagellum. Fusion of zoospore results in zoospore-like structures with multiple flagella (Supp.
1119 Figure 1A in [37]). Zoospore release mechanism is yet-unclear. Single, spherical to ovoid
1120 terminal sporangia are produced. Large, swollen sporangiophores are reported (Figure 1E, 1F in
1121 [37]), with a septum observed at the base of the sporangia. Sporangial neck is constricted with a
1122 narrow neck port (Figure 1H in [37]). Capable of prolonged survival at 39⁰C. Thick walled
1123 septated structures, possibly a resting stage, observed in older but not younger cultures (Figure
1124 S1 F-G in [37]).

1125 *C. Occurrence.* *Buwchfawromyces* was isolated from feces of an Asian water buffalo (*Bubalus*
1126 *bubalis*, Type species GE09), as well as from cow, sheep, and horse feces [37]. Culture-
1127 independent surveys identified *Buwchfawromyces*-affiliated sequences in cow and red deer from
1128 New Zealand to which the alphanumeric designation SK2 was assigned prior to the isolation of
1129 GE09. Due to a possible mismatch to the utilized primers, no *Buwchfawromyces*-affiliated
1130 sequences were identified in the study by [31]. *Buwchfawromyces*-affiliated sequences were
1131 identified in six out of twenty-one examined fecal samples of wild and domesticated herbivores,
1132 mostly as a small fraction of the community [28].

1133 *D. List of species*

1134 **7.1. *Buwchfawromyces eastonii*** Callaghan et al. et al. 2015 [37].

1135 *Type strain.* GE09 Aberystwyth University biorepositories (Wales), Isotype at Royal Botanic
1136 Gardens, Kew, London (K); and Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Germany (JE).

1137 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* EU414755 and EU414756 (ITS1, 5.8S, ITS2), and
1138 KP205570 (D1/D2 LSU)
1139 *ID in databases:* Mycobank ID: MB550797 (genus) and MB550798 (species); Index Fungorum:
1140 IF550797 (genus) and IF550798 (species); NCBI Taxon ID: 1623672 (genus) and 512029
1141 (species).

1142 **8. *Oontomyces* (Dagar et al. 2015).**

1143 *A. History.* The genus has one species, *O. anksri*, isolated from the forestomach of a Camel
1144 (*Camelus dromedarius*) [36].

1145 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [36]. *Oontomyces* produces monoflagellated
1146 zoospores, exhibits monocentric thalli development, and filamentous rhizoidal growth pattern.
1147 Zoospores are spherical with a single long flagellum (Figure 1a, b in [36]). *Oontomyces* produces
1148 long non-swollen sporangiophores that are separated from the hyphae by a distinct constriction
1149 (Figure 1d, e in [36]). Sporangia are terminal ovoid to elongate (Figure 1e in [36]). Intercalary
1150 rhizoidal swellings also observed (Figure 1G in [36]).

1151 *C. Occurrence.* Isolated from the forestomach of a camel. Sequences affiliated with *Oontomyces*
1152 have been detected in one culture-independent study targeting anaerobic gut fungi from the
1153 Bactrian camel (*Camelus bactrianus*) rumen in China: Xinjiang (unpublished; GenBank
1154 accessions JX944831, JX944837, JX944839, JX944843, JX944846, JX944847, JX944848,
1155 JX944853, JX944859, JX944860, JX944862, JX944864, JX944871, JX944872, JX944873,
1156 JX944879, JX944883, JX944884, JX944887, JX944888, JX944889, JX944891, JX944895,
1157 JX944899, JX944900, JX944902, JX944904, JX944911, JX944912, JX944913, JX944920,
1158 JX944921, JX944925, JX944934, JX944937, JX944940, JX944942, JX944944, JX944946,
1159 JX944947, JX944962, JX944964, JX944967, JX944968, JX944969, JX944976, JX944977).

1160 Broader culture-independent analysis from wide range of herbivores failed to detect
1161 *Oontomyces*-affiliated sequences from all samples examined, suggesting a very narrow host
1162 (Camel), or geographic (Asia) distribution.

1163 *D. List of species:*

1164 **8.1. *Oontomyces anksri*** Dagar et al. 2015 [36].

1165 *Type strain:* SSD-CIB1, Figure 1 in [36].

1166 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* JX017310 (ITS1, 5.8S, ITS2 complete) and JX017314
1167 (D1/D2 LSU)

1168 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB550795 (genus) and MB550796 (species); Index Fungorum:
1169 IF550795 (genus) and IF550796 (species); NCBI taxon ID: 1650676 (genus) and 1212493
1170 (species).

1171 **9. *Pecoramyces* (Hanafy et al. 2017)**

1172 *A. History.* *Pecoramyces* species was isolated from the feces of an Angus steer, and its genome
1173 and transcriptome were sequenced and analyzed in 2013 [12]. The strain was erroneously
1174 classified as a member of the genus *Orpinomyces*. However, subsequent analysis identified clear
1175 morphological and microscopic differences when compared to *Orpinomyces*; and phylogenetic
1176 analysis using ITS1 and D1/D2 LSU loci further affirmed its phylogenetic distinction. Such
1177 results hence justified its accommodation in a new genus, for which the name *Pecoramyces* was
1178 proposed [35]. So far, only one species (*P. ruminantium*) has been described [35].

1179 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [35]. On solid media, *Pecoramyces* forms small
1180 (0.5-1 mm diameter) pinpoint-like colonies. In liquid media, it forms a thick smooth biofilm-like
1181 growth pattern. *Pecoramyces* produces monoflagellated zoospores, exhibits monocentric thalli
1182 development, and filamentous rhizoidal growth pattern. Zoospores are relatively large (7.5 ± 1.5

1183 μm) and are released through a wide apical pore, with the sporangial wall staying intact after
1184 zoospore discharge. Both endogenous and exogenous sporangia are encountered. Endogenous
1185 sporangia are subglobose and ovoid, while exogenous sporangia are spherical or ovoid.
1186 Sporangia display both long and short sporangiophores, with some exhibiting eggcup
1187 morphology or subsporangial swellings. The formation of peculiarly enlarged cells in
1188 *Pecoramyces* with strong morphological resemblance to titan cells (enlarged cells produced by
1189 *Cryptococcus neoformans* in response to exposure to the lung environment and shown to
1190 enhance the survival and propagation of *C. neoformans* [57]) has been observed (Figure 3bi), and
1191 could possibly be a resting stage in its life cycle.

1192 *C. Occurrence.* Isolates belonging to the genus *Pecoramyces* have been isolated from fecal
1193 samples of cow and sheep [12, 35], goat rumen [123, 124], Oryx [28, 101], and Nilgiri Tahr
1194 (*Nilgiritragus hylocrius*) feces. Culture-independent diversity surveys suggest a widespread
1195 distribution pattern and a preference to foregut fermenters [35], although occurrence in hindgut
1196 samples has also been observed [28] as an occasional minor fraction of the community.

1197 *D. List of species*

1198 **9.1 *Pecoramyces ruminantium*** Hanafy et al. 2017 [35].

1199 *Type strain:* C1A, Figure 1a-y in [35].

1200 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* NG_060094.1 (D1/D2 LSU), NR_152323.1 (ITS1,
1201 5.8S, ITS2).

1202 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB552530 (genus) and MB552531 (species);

1203 Index Fungorum: IF552530 (genus) and IF55231 (species); NCBI taxon ID: 1987567 (genus)

1204 and 1987568 (species).

1205 **10. *Feramyces* (Hanfay et al. 2018).**

1206 *A. History.* The genus has one species, *F. austinii*, isolated from the rumen and fecal samples of
1207 deer and wild Barbary sheep (*Ammotragus lervia*) [71].

1208 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [71]. On solid media, *Feramyces* produces
1209 medium-sized (3–7 mm), circular, beige colonies with well-defined dark center and filamentous
1210 edges on solid media. In liquid media, *Feramyces* displays a thick biofilm growth pattern.
1211 *Feramyces* produces polyflagellated zoospores, exhibits monocentric thalli development, and
1212 filamentous rhizoidal growth pattern. Zoospores are relatively large (6.5–13 μm), with 7–16
1213 flagella. Zoospore release occurs through sporangial apical pore, with sporangia staying intact.
1214 Long, coiled sporangiophores with subsporangial swelling are observed. Both endogenous and
1215 exogenous sporangial development are produced, with endogenous sporangia displaying globose
1216 or pyriform morphology, and exogenous sporangia displaying highly pleomorphic morphologies.
1217 Pseudointercalary sporangia are sometimes observed. Hyphal growth is extensive with
1218 constrictions observed at regular intervals in wide hyphae.

1219 *C. Occurrence.* Isolated from the rumen and fecal samples of deer and wild Barbary sheep [71] in
1220 the USA and the Czech Republic (Kateřina Fliegerová, personal communication). Prior to its
1221 isolation, sequences affiliated with the genus *Feramyces* were identified in fecal samples from
1222 Giraffe (*Giraffa camelopardalis*), Okapi (*Okapi johnstoni*), and greater Kudu (*Tragelaphus*
1223 *strepsiceros*) with the alphanumeric designation AL6 [31]. Subsequent work identified its
1224 occurrence in multiple wild and domesticated samples, with preference to sheep and deer hosts
1225 [28].

1226 *D. List of species*

1227 **10.1. *Feramyces austinii*** Hanfay et al. 2018 [71]

1228 *Type strain.* F3a (Oklahoma State University Culture Collection, Figure 2h in [71]).

1229 *GenBank sequences accession numbers_* MG584193 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-D1/D2 LSU).
1230 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID MB823650 (genus) and MB823651 (species); Index Fungorum
1231 Registration Identifier: IF823650 (genus) and IF823651 (species); NCBI taxon ID: 2683847
1232 (genus) and 2170546 (species)

1233 **11. *Liebetanzomyces* (Joshi et al. 2018).**

1234 *A. History.* The genus currently has one species, *L. polymorphus*, isolated from goat rumen in
1235 2018 [73].

1236 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [73]. On solid media, colonies are small, beige
1237 to brown (1-2 mm) with a dense central core of sporangial structures. Young newly formed
1238 sporangia are developed at the edges of colonies (Figure 1 b-c in [73]). In liquid media, it
1239 produces a thin loose beige biofilm (Figure 1d in [73]). Isolation from enrichments is usually
1240 achieved after prolonged incubation (3 weeks), indicating slow growth. *Liebetanzomyces*
1241 produces monoflagellated zoospores, exhibits monocentric thalli development, and filamentous
1242 rhizoidal growth pattern. Zoospores are average sized (5–6 µm), monoflagellated. Zoospore
1243 release mechanism is yet unclear. Endogenous, exogenous, and occasionally pseudointercalary
1244 sporangia are observed with highly pleomorphic morphology including globose, ellipsoid,
1245 clavate, ovoid, and irregular shaped (Figure 2 in [73]). Sporangia with papillae is observed
1246 (Figure 3d in [73]). Upon maturity, a septum is developed at the base of sporangia (Figure 3b-e
1247 in [73], note the star). Both short and long sporangiophores are observed for exogenous
1248 sporangia, with occasional constriction at the base of the sporangiophores (Figure 3e in [73]).
1249 Rhizoids are filamentous and highly branched.

1250 *C. Occurrence.* *Liebetanzomyces* strains were isolated from goat rumen [73], as well as cow
1251 feces, and Barbary sheep (Hanafy, unpublished). Culture-independent analysis indicated a

1252 relatively rare distribution pattern in nature, being identified only in a few samples usually in
1253 larger studies (cow, sheep, and llama in [31], cow in [30], and alpaca, Aoudad sheep, blackbuck
1254 antelope, and oryx in [28]), and invariably constituting an minor fraction of the community when
1255 encountered. Members of this clade have been given the alphanumeric designation SP4 prior to
1256 their isolation [30].

1257 *D. List of species:*

1258 **11.1. *Liebetanzomyces polymorphus*.** Joshi et al. 2018 [73]

1259 *Type strain.* Holotype: strain G1SC (collection of microorganisms of Agharkar Research
1260 Institute, Pune, India). An isotype was deposited at Aberystwyth University biorepository,
1261 Wales.

1262 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* MH468765 (ITS1, 5.8S, ITS2) and MH468763 (D1/D2
1263 LSU)

1264 *ID in databases.* MycoBank ID MB554794 (genus), and MB554795 (species); Index Fungorum:
1265 IF554794 (genus) and IF554795 (species); NCBI taxon ID 547816 (genus), and 2219670
1266 (species).

1267 **12. *Agriosomyces* (Hanafy et al. 2021)**

1268 *A. History.* The genus currently has one species, *A. longus*, isolated from feces of a wild sheep
1269 (Mouflon sheep, *Ovis gmelini*) as well as a Boer goat [55].

1270 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [55]. On solid media, *Agriosomyces* forms
1271 small, light brown, circular colonies. In liquid media, it forms a thin biofilm-like growth.

1272 *Agriosomyces* produces monoflagellated zoospores, exhibits monocentric thalli development,
1273 and filamentous rhizoidal growth pattern. Zoospores are small ($4 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{m}$), monoflagellated,
1274 with extremely long flagella (5-6 times the zoospore size). Zoospores are released through

1275 dissolution and rupturing of the sporangial wall. Sporangiohores exhibit sub-sporangial
1276 swelling and the sporangial neck is constricted with a narrow neck port. Endogenous and
1277 exogenous sporangia are observed. Sporangia are globose and very homogenous, with very low
1278 level of pleomorphism observed.

1279 *C. Occurrence.* Isolated from fecal samples of wild (mouflon) sheep and Boer Goat [55]. A
1280 recent culture-independent survey suggests a limited ecological distribution, being encountered
1281 in few (6/21; goat, deer, sheep and Alpaca) animals, and representing >1% of the community in
1282 only two samples (the Mouflon and Boer goat samples from which they were isolated).

1283 *D. List of species:*

1284 **12.1. *Agriosomyces longus*** Hanafy et al. 2020 [55]

1285 *Type strain.* MS2 (Oklahoma State University Culture Collection), Figure 2g in [55]

1286 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* MK882010-MK882013 (ITS1), MK881996 (D1–D2
1287 LSU); and MT085708-MT085709 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-D1/D2 LSU).

1288 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB830737 (genus) and MB830738 (species); Index Fungorum:
1289 IF830737 (genus) and IF830738 (species); NCBI taxon ID: 2710854 (genus) and 2710868
1290 (species).

1291 **13. *Aklioshbomyces* (Hanafy et al. 2021)**

1292 *A. History.* The genus currently has one species, *A. papillarum*, isolated from feces of a white
1293 tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) [55].

1294 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [55]. On solid media, *Aklioshbomyces* forms
1295 small beige, circular colonies with a brown central core. In liquid media, it produces heavy
1296 growth of thick biofilms that firmly attaches to the tube's glass surface. *Aklioshbomyces*
1297 produces monoflagellated zoospores, exhibits monocentric thalli development, and filamentous

1298 rhizoidal growth pattern. Zoospores are medium sized (4.5–7.4 μm) and mostly monoflagellated.
1299 Exogenous and Endogenous sporangia, as well as pseudointercalary sporangia are observed. No
1300 morphological differences were detected between endogenous and exogenous sporangia, with
1301 the most common morphologies being ovoid, globose, obpyriform, and ellipsoidal. **Most**
1302 Sporangia were papillated with one or two papillae, thought to facilitate zoospore release.
1303 Sporangiphores are unbranched with widely varying lengths from a few microns to 230 μm .
1304 *C. Occurrence.* *Aklioshbomyces* type strain was isolated from white tailed deer feces.
1305 Interestingly, culture-independent analysis suggests an extremely limited distribution: in a survey
1306 of 21 animals, it was only identified in high proportion in the same white-tailed deer fecal
1307 sample from which it was isolated. In the four additional samples it was identified, it represented
1308 a minor (<1%) fraction of the anaerobic fungal community [55]. This preference to a single deer
1309 species is extremely rare within the Neocallimastigomycota, in contrast to the more common
1310 observed preferences to an animal family (e.g. *Cyllamyces* preference for Bovidae, or
1311 *Khoyollomyces* for Equidae), or a gut type (e.g. *Pecoramyces* for foregut fermenters).
1312 *D. List of species:*
1313 **13.1. *Aklioshbomyces papillarum*.** Hanafy et al. 2020 [55].
1314 *Type strain.* WT-2 (Oklahoma State University Culture Collection, Figure 3m in [55]).
1315 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* MT085737-MT085741 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-D1/D2 LSU).
1316 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB830735 (genus) and MB830736 (species); Index Fungorum
1317 IF830735 (genus), and IF830736 (species); NCBI taxon ID: 2710855 (genus) and 2710861
1318 (species).
1319 **14. *Capellomyces* (Hanafy et al. 2021)**
1320 *A. History.* Isolates representing two different species (*C. foraminis* and *C. elongatus*) were
1321 isolated from fecal samples of a wild boar goat (USA), and domesticated goat (India),

1322 respectively, and reported in the same manuscript [55]. While displaying a high level of ITS1
1323 and D1/D2 LSU sequence identity, multiple growth and microscopic differences were identified,
1324 justifying their accommodation into two distinct species.

1325 *B. Type:* BGB-11 (Oklahoma State University Culture Collection, Figure 4n in [55])

1326 *C. GenBank sequences accession numbers.* AY997042 (ITS1, 5.8S, ITS2) and DQ273829
1327 (D1/D2 LSU).

1328 *D. ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB830739; Index Fungorum: IF830739; NCBI taxon ID:
1329 2710856.

1330 *E. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [55]. Members of the genus *Capellomyces* form
1331 small white to beige colonies on solid media, and thin biofilm growth in liquid media. Strains
1332 exhibit monocentric thalli development, filamentous rhizoids, and monoflagellated zoopores.
1333 Endogenous and exogenous sporangial development patterns have been observed.

1334 *F. Occurrence.* The genus *Capellomyces* was isolated from fecal samples of Boer goat and
1335 domestic goat, suggesting a preference to goats' alimentary tract. An isolate assigned to the
1336 genus *Anaeromyces* and obtained from goat rumen (*Anaeromyces* sp. GA-04 GenBank accession
1337 FJ912851.1) exhibits high sequence similarity to *Capellomyces* (1.2% average ITS1 sequence
1338 divergence between various clones of *Capellomyces* and *Anaeromyces* sp. GA-04). Peculiarly,
1339 sequences affiliated with the genus *Capellomyces* were not identified in a recent D1/D2 LSU-
1340 based culture-independent diversity survey of 21 animals, which might be attributed to a
1341 mismatch to the Neocallimastigomycota-specific reverse primer employed [28].

1342 *G. List of species.*

1343 **14.1. *Capellomyces foraminis*** Hanafy et al. 2020 [55] from the feces of a wild Boer goat.

1344 *Type strain.* BGB-11 (Oklahoma State University Culture Collection, Figure 4n in [55]).

1345 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* MK882007–MK882009 (ITS1) and MK881975 (D1/D2
1346 LSU).

1347 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB830740; Index Fungorum Registration Identified: IF830740;
1348 NCBI taxon ID: 2710863

1349 *Diagnosis.* Detailed description in provided in Hanafy et al. 2020 [55]. In addition to features
1350 provided in the genus description, the following features were observed: Zoospores are average-
1351 sized (5.5 µm), and liberated through a wide apical pore at the top of the sporangia followed by
1352 sporangial wall collapse. Endogenous sporangia are ellipsoidal and ovoid. Sporangiohores are
1353 unbranched, ranging in length between 20 and 150 µm, with some ending in subsporangial
1354 swellings. Exogenous sporangia are ovoid, ellipsoidal, or globose.

1355 **14.2. *Capellomyces elongatus*** Hanafy et al. 2020 [55] from the feces of a domesticated goat.

1356 *Type strain.* GFKJa1916 (Agharkar Research Institute, Pune, India culture collection, Figure 5k
1357 in [55])

1358 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* MK775315 (ITS1); MK775304 (D1/D2 LSU),
1359 MT085701.1 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-D1/D2 LSU)

1360 *ID in databases:* Mycobank ID: MB830869; Index Fungorum Registration Identified: IF830869;
1361 NCBI taxon ID: 2710862

1362 *Diagnosis.* Detailed description in Hanafy et al [55]. In addition to features provided in the genus
1363 description, the following features were observed: Zoospores are average-sized (4-5 µm).
1364 Endogenous sporangia are more pleomorphic when compared to *C. foraminis* displaying
1365 cylindrical, elongate, globose, subglobose, ellipsoid, and obovoid morphologies.
1366 Sporangiohores are extremely long (up to 300 µm in some cases), and multispore thalli
1367 are commonly observed (i.e. two exogenous sporangia developing on the same sporangiohore).

1368 Exogenous sporangia are ovoid and globose

1369 **15. *Ghazallomyces* (Hanafy et al. 2021)**

1370 *A. History.* The genus has one species *G. constrictus*, isolated from the feces of an Axis deer
1371 (*Axis axis*) [55].

1372 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [55]. On solid media, *Ghazallomyces* produces
1373 small circular colonies with a white to light brown central core. In liquid media, *Ghazallomyces*
1374 produces a thick white biofilm growth. *Ghazallomyces* produces polyflagellated zoospores,
1375 exhibits monocentric thallus development, and filamentous rhizoidal growth pattern. Zoospores
1376 are average-sized, with 7-14 flagella, and are released through an apical pore followed by
1377 collapse of the sporangial wall. Endogenous and Exogenous sporangia are produced, both of
1378 which are highly pleomorphic, and displaying tightly constricted necks with narrow ports. Fine
1379 septum formation at the base of the sporangia is observed. The empty zoospore cyst remains as a
1380 persistent swollen structure at the base of sporangiophore during exogenous thallus development.

1381 *C. Occurrence.* *Ghazallomyces* was isolated from the feces of an Axis deer. Interestingly,
1382 culture-independent survey of 21 samples only identified it in the sample from which it was
1383 isolated, suggesting an extremely rare ecological distribution pattern.

1384 *D. List of species*

1385 **15.1. *Ghazallomyces constrictus*** Hanafy et al. 2020 [55]

1386 *Type strain:* Axs-31 (Oklahoma State University Culture Collection), Figure 6h in [55].

1387 *GenBank sequences accession numbers:* MK882043-MK882046 (ITS1) and MK881971 (D1/D2
1388 LSU)

1389 *ID in databases* Mycobank ID MB830733 (genus) and MB830734 (species); Index Fungorum
1390 Registration Identifier IF830733 (genus), and IF830734 (species); NCBI taxon ID: 2710857

1391 **16. *Joblinomyces* (Hanafy et al. 2021)**

1392 *A. History.* The genus has one species, *J. apicalis*, isolated from the feces of domesticated goat
1393 and sheep [55].

1394 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [55]. On solid media, *Joblinomyces* produces
1395 small colonies with a dark central core surrounded by long and thin radiating rhizoids. In liquid
1396 media, *Joblinomyces* produces a thin biofilm. *Joblinomyces* produces monoflagellated zoospores,
1397 exhibits monocentric thallus development, and a filamentous rhizoidal growth pattern. Zoospores
1398 are medium-sized (5-6 μm), monoflagellated (1-2 flagella), and are released through the gradual
1399 dissolution of a wide apical portion of the sporangial wall, resulting in the formation of an empty
1400 cup-shaped sporangium. Long unbranched sporangiophores (20-80 μm) are observed.

1401 Endogenous and exogenous sporangia are globose, subglobose, ovoid, and obovoid.

1402 *C. Occurrence.* Isolated from domestic goats and sheep feces [55]. Members of this clade have
1403 been given the alphanumeric designation AL5 prior to their isolation [31]. *Joblinomyces*
1404 sequences were encountered in 14/30 samples examined in [31] mainly in foregut fermenters
1405 where they typically represented a minor fraction of the overall anaerobic gut fungal community
1406 within a specific sample, with the exception of a domesticated goat sample where the genus
1407 represented 19.6% of the total anaerobic gut fungal community [31]. In a subsequent culture-
1408 independent study, *Joblinomyces* sequences were encountered in 3/ 21 samples (Mouflon sheep,
1409 Aoudad sheep, and Fallow deer), only representing a significant member of the anaerobic gut
1410 fungal community in the Fallow deer sample (77.12%). This suggests a fairly limited distribution
1411 pattern, and a relative preference for foregut over hindgut fermenters.

1412 *D. List of species:*

1413 **16.1. *Joblinomyces apicalis*.** Hanafy et al. 2020 [55].

1414 *Type strain:* Strain GFH683, Figure 7c in [55].
1415 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* MK910278–MK910282 (ITS1) and MK910268–
1416 MK910272 (D1/D2 LSU)
1417 *ID in databases:* Mycobank ID: MB830867 (genus) and MB830868 (species), Index Fungorum
1418 Registration Identifier IF830867 (genus), and IF830868 (species), NCBI Taxon ID: 2710858
1419 (genus) and 2710865 (species).

1420 **17. *Khoyollomyces* (Hanafy et al. 2021)**

1421 *A. History.* The genus has one species, *K. ramosus*, isolated from the feces of Zebra and
1422 domesticated horses [55].

1423 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [55]. On solid media, *Khoyollomyces* forms
1424 small yellow to yellowish brown irregularly shaped colonies. In liquid media, it generates a loose
1425 growth pattern, and exhibits a sand-like appearance resembling patterns generally observed with
1426 bulbous genera. *Khoyollomyces* produces monoflagellated zoospores, exhibits monocentric
1427 thallus development, and a highly branched filamentous rhizoidal system. Zoospores are
1428 average-sized (6 µm) and are liberated through a wide apical pore at the top of the sporangia.
1429 Long sporangiophores ranging in length from 20 up to 400 µm are typically observed. The genus
1430 is characterized by multispore-bearing thalli, with the majority of sporangiophores being branched
1431 and bearing two to four sporangia. Endogenous, exogenous, and pseudo-intercalary sporangia
1432 are all observed. Endogenous sporangia are small and subglobose, while exogenous sporangia
1433 are larger and more pleomorphic (heart, ovoid, pyriform).

1434 *C. Occurrence.* Isolated from the feces of Zebra and horses [55, 101], Callaghan and Griffith
1435 unpublished). Members of this clade have been given the alphanumeric designation AL1 prior to
1436 their isolation [31]. Culture-independent analysis identified their prevalence as a significant

1437 component of the fungal community in multiple hindgut herbivores, especially those associated
1438 with the family Equidae e.g. horses and Zebras [28, 31]

1439 *D. List of species:*

1440 **17.1 *Khoyollomyces ramosus*** Hanafy et al. 2020 [55]

1441 *Type strain.* ZS-33, Figure 8j in [55]

1442 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* MK882019 (ITS1) and MK881981 (D1–D2 28SrDNA)

1443 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB830741 (genus) and MB830742 (species), Index Fungorum

1444 Registration Identifier IF830741 (genus) and IF830742 (species). NCBI taxon ID: 2710859

1445 (genus) and 2710867 (species).

1446 **18. *Tahromyces* (Hanafy et al. 2021)**

1447 *A. History.* The genus has one species *T. munnarensis* isolated from the feces of Nilgiri Tahr
1448 goats [55].

1449 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [55]. On solid media, *Tahromyces* produces
1450 small colonies with a compact center and filamentous edges. In liquid media, growth occurs as a
1451 thin biofilm attached to the glass surface. *Tahromyces* produces monoflagellated zoospores,
1452 exhibits monocentric thallus development, and a filamentous rhizoidal growth pattern. Zoospores
1453 are relatively small (3-4 μm) and are released via irregular dissolution of the sporangial wall.

1454 Endogenous sporangia are globose, ovoid, and obovoid, with some showing subsporangial
1455 swelling. Exogenous sporangia are also globose, ovoid, and obovoid. Sporangiphores are short,
1456 some of which ending with subsporangial swellings with or without a constricted neck (between
1457 12 and 20 μm). Septum formation at the base of some mature sporangia is observed.

1458 *C. Occurrence.* Isolated from the feces of Nilgiri Tahr, a mountain goat indigenous to India.

1459 Members have not been identified so far in culture-independent analysis, possibly reflecting its

1460 restricted host (Nigleri Tahr), or geographical (India) distribution.

1461 *D. List of species:*

1462 **18.1 *Tahromyces munnarensis*** Hanafy et al. 2020 [55].

1463 *Type strain:* TDFKJa193, Figure 9h in [55]

1464 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* MT085675 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-D1/D2 LSU); MK775321

1465 (ITS1); MK775310 (D1–D2 28S rDNA)

1466 *ID in databases:* MycoBank ID MB830865 (genus) and MB830866 (species); Index Fungorum

1467 Registration Identifier IF830865 (genus), and IF830866 (species); NCBI taxon ID: 2710860

1468 (genus), and 2710866 (species).

1469 **19. *Aestipascuomyces* (Stabel et al. 2020)**

1470 *A. History.* Members of the genus *Aestipascuomyces* were simultaneously and independently

1471 isolated by two research groups in 2020 from fecal samples of Alpaca and Sheep [75]. Only one

1472 species, *A. dupliciliberans*, has been described.

1473 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [75]. On solid media, *Aestipascuomyces* forms

1474 medium-sized (2–5 mm) white filamentous colonies with a white center of sporangia. In liquid

1475 media, *Aestipascuomyces* forms a distinctly heavy biofilm growth. *Aestipascuomyces* produces

1476 polyflagellated zoospores, exhibits monocentric thallus development, and a filamentous rhizoidal

1477 growth pattern. Zoospores are relatively large (5–14 μm), with 7–20 flagella, and are released

1478 through an apical pore as well as by sporangial wall rupturing. Utilization of this dual spore

1479 release mechanism in a single strain has not been observed in other Neocallimastigomycota

1480 genera. Unbranched sporangiophores ranging in length between 10 and 300 μm , many of which

1481 displaying subsporangial swelling. Pleomorphic endogenous and Exogenous sporangia are

1482 observed. Sporangial necks are often tightly constricted.

1483 *C. Occurrence.* Isolated from the feces of alpaca and sheep [75]. Members of this clade have
1484 been identified in fecal samples of sheep and deer and given the alphanumeric designation SK4
1485 prior to their isolation [125, 126]. A recent survey of 21 fecal samples identified its occurrence as
1486 a major component in the sheep sample from which it was isolated, and as an extremely minor
1487 component of five additional samples. A possible positive correlation between *Aestipascuomyces*
1488 abundance and grazing in summer pastures has been suggested [75].

1489 *D. List of species*

1490 **19.1 *Aestipascuomyces dupliciliberans*** Stabel et al. 2020, [75].

1491 *Type strain.* R4 (Oklahoma State University Culture Collection, Figure 2b in [75].

1492 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* MW019494- MW0194497 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-D1/D2
1493 LSU).

1494 *ID in databases.* Mycobank ID: MB837524 (genus) and MB837526 (species); Index Fungorum
1495 Registration Identifier IF837524 (genus), and IF837526 (species), NCBI taxon ID: 2789199
1496 (genus), and 2789200 (species).

1497 **20. *Paucimyces* (Hanafy et al. 2021)**

1498 *A. History.* The genus has one species, *P. polynucleatus*, isolated from the feces of a wild
1499 blackbuck antelope (Indian Antelope, *Antelope cervicapra*) [72].

1500 *B. Diagnosis.* Detailed description is provided in [72]. On solid media, *Paucimyces* produces
1501 medium sized white compact circular colonies with no dark center. In liquid media, thin loose
1502 biofilm-like growth is observed, with occasional clumping that appears as small, loose, fragile
1503 spherical structures at the bottom of the culture tube. *Paucimyces* produces monoflagellated
1504 zoospores, exhibits polycentric thallus development, and a filamentous rhizoidal growth pattern.
1505 The relatively large (6-10 μm) zoospores are released through a wide apical pore at the top of the

1506 sporangia, with the sporangial wall staying intact after the discharge. The polycentric thalli
1507 exhibit a highly branched nucleated filamentous rhizomycelium. During thallus development,
1508 hyphal tips swell to form spherical vesicles, from which multiple sporangiophores arise (Figure
1509 2h-i in [72]). Each sporangiophore bears one sporangium at its end. In many cases, sporangia
1510 develop on the spherical vesicles without sporangiophores. Sporangia are mainly ovoid. Basal
1511 walls are formed to separate the mature sporangia from the sporangiophores (Figure 2j-k in
1512 [72]). Old cultures lose the capacity for the production of sporangia and only produce
1513 sporangiophores initials.

1514 *C. Occurrence.* Isolated from the feces of a wild blackbuck (Indian Antelope) [72]. Members of
1515 this clade have been identified in fecal samples in a recent culture-independent study [28], and
1516 were given the alphanumeric designation RH5 prior to their isolation. Interestingly, *Paucimyces*-
1517 affiliated sequences were identified almost entirely in sheep samples in this study, suggesting a
1518 possible genus preference for the ovine alimentary tract.

1519 *D. List of species:*

1520 **20.1. *Paucimyces polynucleatus*** Hanafy et al. 2021 [72]

1521 *Type strain.* strain BB-3 (Oklahoma State University Culture Collection), Figure 2c in [72].

1522 *GenBank sequences accession numbers.* MW694896-MW64898 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-D1/D2 LSU).

1523 *ID in databases:* Mycobank ID: MB838953 (genus) and MB838954 (species); Index Fungorum

1524 Registration Identifier: IF838953 (genus), and IF838954 (species), NCBI taxon ID: NA.

1525

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1527

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1529 reviewing the manuscript.

1530

1531 **VII. Conflicts of Interest.** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

1532 **VIII. Figure legends:**

1533 **Figure 1.** Timeline highlighting salient events in Neocallimastigomycota discovery and progress
1534 in description of novel genera. References reporting a specific contribution are in parenthesis.

1535 **Figure 2.** Neocallimstigomycota Life Cycle.

1536 **Figure 3. Microscopic features observed in various stages of the Neocallimastigomycota life**
1537 **cycle with emphasis on taxonomically informative traits. Zoospore flagellation (a-d):**

1538 Monoflagellated zoospores with a single (a, *Pecoramyces ruminantium* strain C1A), two (b,

1539 *Pecoramyces ruminantium* strain C1A), three (c, *Aklioshbomyces papillarum* strain WT2), or

1540 multiple (d, *Neocallimastix cf. frontalis* strain Hef5) flagella. *Zoospore encystment (e-f):*

1541 Zoospore cyst and flagellar shedding (e) with the shed flagella forming a bead-like structure at

1542 the point of former attachment (arrow, *Pecoramyces ruminantium* strain C1A), (f) shed flagella

1543 from a polyflagellated zoospore (*Feramyces austinii* strain F3a) . Note the rounding of flagellar

1544 body following encystment compared to zoospore figures a, and c. *Spore germination (g-h):*

1545 development of a single (g) germ tube (*Pecoramyces ruminantium* strain C1A), and two (white

1546 arrows) germ tubes (*Feramyces austinii* strain F3a). *Rhizoidal system development:* branching of

1547 germ tubes (i-k, *Pecoramyces ruminantium* strain C1A). *Monocentric thalli (l-s):* endogenous

1548 sporangial development (l-o; l: *Joblinomyces apicalis* strain GFH686, m: *Ghazallomyces*

1549 *constrictus* stain Axs-31, and n-o: *Pecoramyces ruminantium* strain C1A), pseudo-intercalary

1550 sporangial development (p: *Aklioshbomyces papillarum* strain WT2, and q: *Feramyces austinii*

1551 strain F3a), exogenous sporangial development (r: *Ghazallomyces constrictus* stain Axs-31, and

1552 s: *Aestipasquomyces dupliciliberans* strain R4) with rhizoidal (Rz) development on one end of

1553 the zoospore cyst (Zc), sporangiophore (Sp) development on the other end of the zoospore cyst,

1554 and a sporangium (S) developing at the end of sporangiophore. In monocentric thalli, nuclei stay

1555 within the spore and do not enter the germ tube during germination, resulting in an anucleated
1556 rhizoidal system (n and o: *Pecoramyces ruminantium* strain C1A, and s: *Aestipascuomyces*
1557 *dupliciliberans* strain R4). *Polycentric thalli (t-z)*: nuclei migrate out of the zoospore cysts into
1558 the germ tube, which elongates and branches. Subsequent division of the nuclei give rise to
1559 nucleated rhizoids, referred to as rhizomycelia (t: *Paucimyces polynucleatus* strain BB-3, and u:
1560 *Orpinomyces cf. joyonii* strain D4A). Terminal sporangial development (v-x, *Paucimyces*
1561 *polynucleatus* strain BB-3) at the end of sporangiophores (v), on spherical vesicles (w), or at the
1562 end of sporangiophores on spherical vesicles (x). Intercalary sporangial development (y,
1563 *Orpinomyces cf. joyonii* strain D4A, and z, *Orpinomyces intercalaris* strain SKP4) either as a
1564 lateral outgrowth of the hyphae (y), or as a result of hyphal expansion (z). *Sporangiophores (aa-*
1565 *ag)*: Short sporangiophore (Sp) (aa, arrow, *Tahromyces munnarensis* strain TDFKJa1924). Long
1566 sporangiophore (ab, *Aestipascuomyces dupliciliberans* strain R4). Eggcup-shaped
1567 sporangiophore (ac, arrow, *Pecoramyces ruminantium* strain S4B). Wide flattened
1568 sporangiophore (ad, *Feramyces austinii* strain F3a). Sporangium ending with sub-sporangial
1569 swelling (ae, arrow, *Pecoramyces ruminantium* strain S4B, arrow). Branched sporangiophore on
1570 monocentric multisporangiate thalli with two (af, *Khoyollomyces ramosus* strain ZS-33) and four
1571 (ag, *Khoyollomyces ramosus* strain ZS-33) sporangia. *Sporangial shapes (ah-as) and features*
1572 *(at-ax)*: globose sporangium with tightly constricted neck (ah, *Feramyces austinii* strain F3a),
1573 ellipsoidal sporangium with constriction at the middle, a tightly constricted neck and a narrow
1574 neck port (ai, *Ghazallomyces constrictus* stain Axs-31), ovoid sporangium with a broad neck and
1575 wide neck port (aj, *Feramyces austinii* strain F3a), bowling pin-shaped (ak, *Ghazallomyces*
1576 *constrictus* stain Axs-31) sporangium, egg-shaped sporangium (al, *Feramyces austinii* strain
1577 F3a), and pyriform sporangium with a basal wall (arrow) forming to separate mature sporangia

1578 from sporangiophores (am, *Ghazallomyces constrictus* stain Axs-31). Heart-shaped sporangium
1579 (an, *Feromyces austinii* strain F3a), triangular sporangium (ao, *Feromyces austinii* strain F3a),
1580 mucronate sporangium with a pointed apex (ap, *Anaeromyces mucronatus* strain BRL7),
1581 elongated sporangium (aq, *Ghazallomyces constrictus* stain Axs-31), ellipsoidal sporangia with
1582 no constrictions (ar, *Aklioshbomyces papillarum* strain WT2), rhomboidal sporangium (as,
1583 *Aestipascuomyces dupliciliberans* strain R4). Sporangia with a single (at), and double (au)
1584 papillae (*Aklioshbomyces papillarum* strain WT2). In polycentric species, thalli could lose the
1585 ability to produce sporangia and only produce sporangiophores initials (arrows) (av, *Paucimyces*
1586 *polynucleatus* strain BB-3), or could produce sterile sporangia (aw, *Paucimyces polynucleatus*
1587 strain BB-3). In such cases, isolates grow by rhizomycelial fragmentation (ax, *Orpinomyces* sp.
1588 strain GKP14). *Spore released mechanisms (ay-ba)*: An apical pore formed at the top of the
1589 sporangia and the sporangial walls remained intact (ay, *Pecoromyces ruminantium* strain S4B),
1590 Sporangial wall rupture (az, *Aestipascuomyces dupliciliberans* strain R4). Complete dissolution
1591 of sporangial wall (ba: *Aestipascuomyces dupliciliberans* strain R4). *Rhizoidal growth patterns*
1592 *(bb-be) and structures (bf-bi)*: Filamentous (bb, *Neocallimastix cf. cameroonii* strain G3) versus
1593 bulbous (bc, *Caecomyces cf. communis* strain DS1) rhizoidal growth patterns. Wide hyphae with
1594 multiple constrictions occurring at regular intervals resulting in a distinctive sausage-shaped
1595 morphology (bd, *Anaeromyces contortus* strain O2), or at irregular intervals (be, *Orpinomyces cf.*
1596 *joyonii* strain D4A). Hyphal coils (bf and bg), and appressoria (bh and bi) in *Anaeromyces*
1597 *contortus* strain O2. *Resistant structures (bj, Khyollomyces ramosus* strain HoCal4.A2.2), and
1598 enlarged titan cell-like structures (bk, *Pecoromyces ruminantium* strain C1A).

1599 **Figure 4.** (A) A cartoon of the rRNA locus encompassing the SSU rRNA (18S), the 5.8S rRNA,
1600 and the LSU rRNA (28S) genes with the two inter-transcribed spacer regions (ITS1 and ITS2).

1601 Sizes of various loci are not to scale. (B-C) Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree constructed
1602 using the ITS1 region (B), and D1/D2 region of the LSU rRNA genes (C) of the type species of
1603 all described Neocallimastigomycota species. For constructing both trees, sequences were
1604 aligned using the MAFFT aligner with the –auto flag and the default parameters for gap
1605 extension and gap opening penalties and maximum likelihood tree was constructed in FastTree.
1606 Bootstrap values are based on 100 replicates and are shown for branches with >50% bootstrap
1607 support. (B) ITS1 region sequences of all type species with the exception of *Orpinomyces*
1608 *intercalaris* (for which no available ITS1 sequence was available) were utilized to construct the
1609 tree. All clone sequences were used when available. For *Caecomycetes churrovis*, *Piromycetes*
1610 *finnis*, and *Neocallimastix lanati*, the ITS1 regions were extracted from their corresponding
1611 genomic sequences. Detailed sub-trees for the genera *Neocallimastix* and
1612 *Caecomycetes/Cyllamyces*, and *Anaeromyces* are shown in Figures 5, 7, and 8, respectively. (C)
1613 D1/D2 region of the LSU rRNA genes sequences from type species for all described
1614 Neocallimastigomycota taxa (with the exception of *Anaeromyces robustus*, *Caecomycetes*
1615 *sympodialis* and *Cyllamyces icaris* for which D1/D2 sequences are not available) were utilized to
1616 construct the tree.

1617 **Figure 5.** (A). Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree constructed using the ITS1 region of
1618 *Neocallimastix* species highlighting the synonymy of *N. hurleyensis* (shown in purple text) to *N.*
1619 *frontalis*, and the synonymy of *N. californiae*, *N. lanate*, and *N. cf. patriciarum* (shown in red
1620 text) to *N. cameronii*. Sequences were aligned using the MAFFT aligner with the –auto flag and
1621 the default parameters for gap extension and gap opening penalties and maximum likelihood tree
1622 was constructed in FastTree. Bootstrap values are based on 100 replicates and are shown for
1623 branches with >50% bootstrap support. (B) Cartoon highlighting the studies that proposed

1624 synonymy of the above species to either *N. frontalis* or *N. cameroonii* using phylogenetic (■),
1625 and/or morphological (●) evidences.

1626 **Figure 6. Additional illustrations of multiple Neocallimastigomycota species using cf.**
1627 **strains from the authors' culture collections.**

1628 *Neocallimastix frontalis* strain Hef5 (a-m): beige circular colonies (up to 2.5 mm) with a dark
1629 center of sporangial structure on agar roll tubes (a), and thin biofilm growth in liquid media (b);
1630 globose zoospores with 9-17 flagella (c); endogenous ellipsoidal (d) and mitten-shaped (e)
1631 sporangia; ovoid exogenous sporangia at the end of a short sporangiophore with an egg-cup like
1632 morphology (f); globose exogenous sporangia at the end of a short sporangiophore with an egg-
1633 cup like morphology (g); ellipsoidal exogenous sporangia at the end of a long sporangiophore
1634 (h); zoospores release through dissolution and rupturing of the entire sporangial wall (i).

1635 *Neocallimastix cf. cameroonii* strain G3 (j-m): globose zoospores with 9-17 flagella (j); globose
1636 (k) and ovoid (l) mature sporangia; zoospore release through a wide apical pore with the
1637 sporangial wall stays intact (m).

1638 *Caecomyces cf. communis* strain DS1 (n-t): *Caecomyces* produces small white granular colonies
1639 (n), and sandy morphology growth in liquid media (o). *Caecomyces cf. communis* strain DS1:
1640 globose monoflagellated zoospores (p). Bulbous rhizoidal system with spherical holdfasts and
1641 both endogenous and exogenous; globose endogenous sporangia (q), ovoid endogenous
1642 sporangia (r), ovoid exogenous sporangia at the end of long tubular sporangiophore (s).
1643 Sporangia detached from the rhizoidal system (t).

1644 *Piromyces cf. communis* strain Jen1 (u-y), and *Piromyces cf. finnis* strain DonB11 (z-ab):
1645 *Piromyces* produces small circular colonies with a dark center of sporangial structure (u), and
1646 exhibits thin biofilm-like growth in liquid medium that firmly attaches to the glass walls of the

1647 tube (v). Sporangia develop both endogenously and exogenously with variable shapes including
1648 elongated (w), spherical (x and ab), ovoid (y), ellipsoidal (z), and diamond-shaped (aa). Some
1649 sporangia have broad neck with broad neck port (o). Short egg-cup shaped sporangiophores are
1650 frequently observed (x and aa).

1651 *Orpinomyces cf. joyonii* strain D4A (ac-aj): *Orpinomyces* forms large (usually >1 cm diameter)
1652 white colonies on agar roll tubes (ac), and a characteristic thick cottony fungal growth (ad) in
1653 liquid media. Narrow and wide hyphae; with the wide hyphae displaying multiple constrictions
1654 at irregular intervals (ae). Old cultures producing sporangiophores initials and no sporangia (af).
1655 (ag-aj) *Orpinomyces cf. joyonii* strain D4A: globose polyflagellated zoospores with 10-25
1656 flagella (ag). Globose terminal sporangia developed at the tip of sporangiophore (ah-ai).
1657 Sporangia developed as a lateral outgrowth of hyphae (aj).

1658 *Cyllamyces cf. aberensis* strains TSB2 (ak-al), CFH681 (am-ap), and BFH688 (aq): *Cyllamyces*
1659 produces granular colonies on agar tubes (ak), and thin loose biofilm-like growth in liquid media
1660 (al). *Cyllamyces* displays monoflagellated zoospores (am), bulbous rhizoidal system with
1661 multiple sporangia, and polycentric thallus with nuclei in the rhizoidal holdfast and the sporangia
1662 (an-ap). In presence of rice straw, *Cyllamyces* sometimes produces elongated rhizoids and
1663 bulbous holdfast (aq).

1664 **Figure 7.** Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree constructed using the ITS1 region of
1665 *Caecomyces*, and *Cyllamyces* species highlighting the clear separation between the two clades
1666 comprising *Caecomyces communis* and *Cyllamyces aberensis*, and the synonymy of *Caecomyces*
1667 *churrovis* (shown in red text) to *Caecomyces communis*. The tree also highlights the peculiar
1668 position of *Cyllamyces icaris* and *Caecomyces sympodialis* (shown in cyan text) separate from
1669 either of the two clades, and suggesting they could belong to a third clade. Sequences were

1670 aligned using the MAFFT aligner with the –auto flag and the default parameters for gap
1671 extension and gap opening penalties and maximum likelihood tree was constructed in FastTree.
1672 Bootstrap values are based on 100 replicates and are shown for branches with >50% bootstrap
1673 support.

1674 **Figure 8.** Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree constructed using the ITS1 region of
1675 representatives of *Anaeromyces-Liebetanzomyces-Capellomyces-Oontomyces* clade. Sequences
1676 were aligned using the MAFFT aligner with the –auto flag and the default parameters for gap
1677 extension and gap opening penalties and maximum likelihood tree was constructed in FastTree.
1678 Bootstrap values are based on 100 replicates and are shown for branches with >50% bootstrap
1679 support.

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2001

Spore

Spore

encystment

germination

Rhizoidal system development

Sporangial development

AGF life cycle

A

A

B

j

k

l

m

0.008

0.04

Additional key morphological characteristics

Large colony size >1cm and thick cottony biofilm

Thick granulated pearl-like growth

Granular colonies and sand-like fungal biofilm

Loose sand-like fungal biofilm

Figure S1. Morphological variations in taxonomically significant features of Neocallimastigomycota. Sporangial variations in *Piromyces communis* (a-h) and *Neocallimastix cameroonii* (i-k) specifically showing papillated sporangium (a-b), multisporangiate sporangia (c-d), short (e) and eggcup sporangiophore (i) and subsporangial swelling (g-h, j-k). Absence of sporangia in *Orpinomyces joyonii* (l) and *Anaeromyces mucronatus* (m). Oval sporangia in *Anaeromyces mucronatus* instead of typical pointed apex (n). A germinating zoospores of *Piromyces communis* (o) giving impression of polyflagellate zoospore. Congregated flagella of *Neocallimastix cameroonii* (p) giving impression of a uniflagellate zoospore.